

National Police Service Officers’ Perception towards Police Reforms in Kenya: A Case Study of Kisumu County

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A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF ARTS AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, DEPARTMENT OF SOCIOLOGY,
PSYCHOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY, MOI UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF REQUIREMENTS FOR
THE AWARD OF MASTER OF ARTS IN SOCIOLOGY.

MOI UNIVERSITY

ABSTRACT

In popular discourse, police reforms in Kenya are promoted by the government and non-state actors as essential for effective service delivery. However, a systematic literature review from 2007 to 2020 reveals that members of the National Police Service (NPS) are often mere recipients of these reforms. This phenomenon, common in many public reform policies, has led to varied responses from NPS members, highlighting the need to investigate their perceptions of police reforms. Guided by Kurt Lewin's theory, this study focused on three specific objectives: investigating police officers' knowledge about police reforms, determining their attitudes towards the reforms, and analyzing their practices regarding the reforms. A descriptive research design was employed, using questionnaires to collect data from a predetermined sample of 200 police officers in both urban and rural areas of Kisumu County. The questionnaire included both open and closed-ended questions. Participants were selected using multi-stage sampling techniques, with the inclusion criterion of having served in the police force for a minimum of seven years at the time of the study. Data collected from the questionnaires was first cleaned, with quantitative data coded and descriptively analyzed using SPSS. Qualitative data from open-ended questions was read, re-read, and thematically analyzed. Both quantitative and qualitative data were used collaboratively to understand police officers' perceptions of the reforms. The study findings show high awareness of police reforms among officers, with a small percentage unaware. Officers associate reforms with various improvements and demonstrate positive attitudes towards increased accountability and community engagement. However, skepticism remains about corruption reduction efforts. A significant number feel excluded from the reform process, indicating a need for better communication and inclusive participation. Individual responses vary, with some officers endorsing reforms for professional growth and others expressing resistance or apprehension. The study recommends developing comprehensive communication strategies and fostering inclusive participation to ensure all officers are informed and involved. Clear articulation of reform goals, addressing implementation challenges, proactively managing resistance, providing training, and establishing monitoring mechanisms are essential for effective reform and enhanced accountability.

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CHAPTER ONE BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The police play a very important role which includes to uphold and enforce the law impartially and to protect life, liberty, property, human rights, and dignity of the members of the public (Koech, 2016). However, the delivery of these services in the Police Service has continuously drawn attention from the public (Ransley Report 2009).

According to East African Bribery Index Report (2011) corruption is one of the most cited impediments to Police service delivery. As noted in the report, the police continue to record high corruption index among most public institutions. For example, corruption index increased from 77 % in 2010 to 81% in 2011 although there was a reduction in the number of police asking for bribes. In all the five East Africa Community, the police ranked number one in corruption (The Star, 22 October, 2011). The World Bank Report (2011) also ranked the Kenya National Police with the highest number of complaints in Kenya. The number of complaints increased from 45% to 60% in the year 2011.

Consequently, corruption has translated into poor public perception toward the police which in turn negatively affect service delivery. Gaines and Kappeler (2015), for instance assert that many people consider the police as corrupt and therefore do not trust them to assist. Hope (2015) also notes that corruption compromises the institutional integrity of policing system and undermines its legitimacy.

Njuguna et al (2013) attributes poor police service delivery to inadequate funding which has led to shortage of personnel and lack of equipment for service delivery. As a consequence, there is weak operational preparedness and logistical capacity for the police to deal with crime. For example, the police do not have a forensic laboratory which is a necessity in dealing with emerging crime. Also, lack of fund to employ more officers has seen the ration between the police and citizen to averages 1:900 which is indeed below the United Nations recommended of 1: 450.

The problem of police service delivery is a major public discourse in Kenya. The mass media, reports by Non-State Agencies and the government have continuously highlighted poor service delivery incidents by the police. These incidents which are often constructed in terms of human rights violation have continued to erode public trust on the police, an important cog of effective policing (Lawi, 2013). Ironically, this focus does not take into account the plight of the police officers. Report commissioned by Government of Kenya (2014), for example, indicated that police officers cited low pay, lack of incentives, poor working and living conditions as factors impeding their service delivery at personal level. This devalues individual factors in service delivery.

The government of Kenya has embarked on structural and organizational reforms to improve police service delivery. This included the improvement of police welfare, enhancing the community policing, improving quick response to crime scenes through increasing of motor vehicles, merging of the two police services, recruitment of the Inspector General of police and his two deputies as well as the establishment of the Independent Police Oversight Authority and the National Police Service Commission (Amnesty International, 2013).

Other reforms also include vetting of police officers. According to The National Police Service Act all members of the National Police Service (NPS) need to undergo vetting to assess their suitability and competence and can only remain in the service when they pass the vetting- Section 7(2) and (3). The section stipulates that the National Police Service Commission (NPSC) is the institution tasked to carry out the vetting, build on confidence and trust in the National Police Service. The main objectives of police vetting is to ensure that the service complies with Chapter Six of the Constitution and the principles of public service as set out in Article 232 of the Constitution and in the Public Officer Ethics Act.

To implement various police reforms, a number Commissions were put in place. Some of these commissions include the National Police Service Commission (N.P.S.C) whose mandate was to vet all police officers. The Independent Policing Oversight Authority (IPOA) which was established through an Act of Parliament published in November 2011 to provide for civilian oversight over the work of the police in Kenya. IPOA is in charge of investigating any complaints related to disciplinary or criminal offenses committed by any member of the Service, whether on its own motion or on receipt of a complaint, and make recommendations to the relevant authorities, including recommendations for prosecution, compensation, internal disciplinary action or any other appropriate relief, and shall make public the response received to these recommendations. The common denominator in all these commissions is that they are headed by civilians who have no working experience in police service. This has created conflict between implementing agencies and members of National Police service (Amnesty International, 2013).

Although these reforms aim at improving service delivery, they were initiated as a response to factors outside the National Police Service. Accordingly, the call for police reform was in response to 2007/2008 post-election violence which saw hundred civilians lose their lives and thousands displaced from their home. The police were heavily indicted. This led to formation of commission of inquiry chaired by Phillip Waki. One of the findings of “Waki Commission” was that the police lacked capacity to contain violence and in some instances they instigated violence by taking political sides. As a result, they recommended police reforms to avert future recurrence of human rights violation (Waki, 2008).

Informed by Waki report, the Government formed a task force on police reforms which was chaired by Justice (Rtd) Philip Ransley. The task force borrowed heavily from the two police strategic plans that is police strategic plan 2003-2007 and 2008-2012 and conducted public hearings which involved oral and written submissions from the public, civil societies and all interested stakeholders. The task force also conducted research from several countries around the world on the world standards and best practices on policing. Notably, members of National police services were involved.

Despite this, the task force came up with over 200 recommendations on police reforms in Kenya; key to which were the merger of the two police forces into one, change of the name from a force to a service, establishment of the office of the Inspector General, establishment of the National Police Service Commission, establishment of the Independent Policing Oversight Authority, establishment of the Internal Affairs Unit, review of the police training curriculum, vetting of all police officers, retraining of all police officers, change of the police ranking structure, purchase of enough operational resources and improvement of the general welfare and terms of service of police officers (Ransley, 2010).

Systematic literature review on Police reforms in Kenya between 2003 and 2020 using data base google search, google scholar, and Jstor which are commonly used by scholars in Kenya revealed non-involvement of members of National Police services in reforms. Findings also revealed no data on emic understanding police reforms. Instead most studies focused on the challenges related to police reforms, institutionalizing of police reforms, police reforms and community policing, and genesis of police reforms. It is only in mass media especially print which highlighted opposition of members of National police service responses to reforms. For example, Gumbihi (2015) reported that some members of National Police Service who were opposed to vetting exercise by National Police service commission threatened the chairman with death threats if he continued with vetting exercise.

Despite opposition to police reforms, no empirical study has been carried out on how members of National police service perceive police reforms as evidenced by systematic literature review since 2003 to 2020. Studies have shown relationship between perception of phenomena and people's subsequent social action (Blurr, 2003, Foucault, 2006, Bacchi, 2010). However, in current police reforms this has not been taken into account in studies focusing on impact of police reforms on service delivery (Gjelsvik, 2020). As noted by Hope (2012) most reforms in public service aimed at service delivery negate internal stakeholders whom are directly impacted by the reforms. This leads the internal stakeholders as passive consumers in reform process. This study therefore endeavors to investigate how the member of National police service (police officers) perceives (police sector) reforms aimed at improving service delivery by specifically investigating their knowledge and attitudes towards the reforms.

A. *Statement of the Problem*

The Kenyan Police Service faces significant challenges in fulfilling its crucial role of upholding the law and protecting public rights and dignity due to widespread corruption and inadequate funding. Reports from the East African Bribery Index (2011) and the World Bank (2011) highlight high corruption levels and numerous complaints against the police, leading to poor public trust and perception (Gaines & Kappeler, 2015; Hope, 2015). Insufficient funding has further exacerbated the situation by causing a shortage of personnel and essential equipment, thus weakening the police's capacity to effectively address crime (Njuguna et al., 2013). Although the government has initiated various structural and organizational reforms, including oversight bodies and vetting processes, these efforts have primarily been reactive responses to external crises like the 2007/2008 post-election violence (Amnesty International, 2013; Waki, 2008).

A review of literature from 2003 to 2020 indicates a lack of focus on the perspectives of police officers, who are the internal stakeholders directly affected by these reforms. Most existing studies have concentrated on challenges, institutionalization, and community policing aspects, without addressing the attitudes and knowledge of the police officers themselves (Gjelsvik, 2020). This gap underscores the necessity for empirical research to investigate police officers' perceptions of the reforms intended to improve service delivery, as their involvement and support are vital for the successful implementation of these initiatives (Hope, 2012).

B. *Objectives*

➤ *General Objective*

The general objective of this study is to investigate perception of police officers towards police reforms in Kisumu County-Kenya.

➤ *Specific Objectives*

- To investigate the police officer's knowledge on police reforms.
- To determine the police officers' attitudes towards police reforms.
- To analyze the practice of police officers towards police reforms

C. Research Questions

➤ *In the Light of the Aforementioned Objectives the Research will Sought to Answer the Following Questions:*

- What is police officers' knowledge on police reforms. perception towards reforms?
- What are police officers' attitudes towards police reforms.
- What are police practices towards police reforms.

D. Justification of the Study

The Kenyan Police Service is a pivotal institution in maintaining law and order, safeguarding human rights, and upholding the rule of law. However, the service delivery of the police has been critically hampered by systemic issues such as corruption, inadequate funding, and operational inefficiencies. The East African Bribery Index (2011) and the World Bank (2011) have underscored the high levels of corruption and numerous complaints against the police, leading to a significant erosion of public trust. Furthermore, insufficient funding has resulted in a lack of essential resources and personnel, weakening the police's ability to effectively combat crime and ensure public safety (Njuguna et al., 2013). Despite the government's efforts to introduce various reforms, these measures have largely been reactive and have not adequately addressed the root causes of inefficiencies within the police service (Amnesty International, 2013; Waki, 2008).

The success of any reform initiative heavily depends on the support and engagement of those directly impacted by the changes. Police officers' perceptions and attitudes towards reforms can significantly influence the outcomes of these initiatives (Hope, 2012). This study is justified as it aims to provide insights into the perspectives of police officers, thereby contributing to the design of more inclusive and effective reform strategies that can enhance the overall service delivery of the Kenyan Police Service

This study is significant as it addresses a critical gap in existing literature by focusing on the perceptions of police officers, who are the primary internal stakeholders directly impacted by the reforms. Previous studies have primarily concentrated on external challenges and institutional aspects of police reforms, neglecting the attitudes and knowledge of the police officers themselves (Gjelsvik, 2020). Understanding the perspectives of police officers is crucial for the successful implementation of reforms, as their support and involvement are essential for improving service delivery and restoring public trust. By investigating the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of police officers towards reforms, this study aims to provide valuable insights that can inform more effective and inclusive reform strategies, ultimately leading to a more efficient and trustworthy police service (Hope, 2012).

E. Scope of the Study

➤ *The Scope of this Study Encompasses the Following Dimensions:*

- **Geographical Scope:** The study focuses on Kisumu County, Kenya. Kisumu County is chosen due to its unique socio-economic dynamics and its representation of broader national issues within the Kenyan Police Service.
- **Population and Sample:** The study targets police officers serving in various capacities within Kisumu County. This includes officers from different ranks and departments to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the perceptions across the entire police service hierarchy.
- **Thematic Scope:** The study investigates three primary areas:
- **Knowledge of Police Reforms:** Investigating awareness and understanding among police officers regarding police reforms.
- **Attitudes towards Police Reforms:** Determining the attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions of police officers towards these reforms, including their perceived benefits and drawbacks.
- **Practices in Response to Police Reforms:** Analyzing the actual practices and behaviors of police officers in response to the reforms, including any changes in their daily operations and interactions with the public.

F. Limitations of the Study

- **Geographical Limitation:** The study is confined to Kisumu County, which may not fully represent the diversity of experiences and perspectives of police officers across different regions of Kenya. The findings might not be generalizable to other counties with different socio-economic and political contexts.
- **Scope of Reforms Considered:** The study focuses on police reforms implemented between 2003 and 2020. Reforms outside this period are not considered, which might omit relevant changes that have occurred either before or after this timeframe, potentially affecting the comprehensiveness of the study.
- **Self-Reported Data:** The study relies on self-reported data from police officers, which can be subject to biases such as social desirability bias or recall bias. Officers may underreport negative perceptions or overstate positive views due to fear of repercussions or a desire to present themselves in a favorable light.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Literature Review

The review covered the issues of police vetting; it also provided vital information on factors that affect police vetting in Kenya. Change Management theories were identified and amplified with various opinions and interpretations.

B. Theoretical Literature

Theoretical Perspective of this study was guided by Kurt Lewin’s theory of change to examine the effects of police reforms on the performance of policing services and explain the research findings. The theory was first proposed by Kurt Lewin (Kritsonis, 2005). This theory explains that change occurs in three phases and each phase is characterized by forces that drive towards the equilibrium or status quo. These forces are the driving and restraining forces. These phases can best be understood with the use of analogy of changes in the shape of a block of ice. The three phases are unfreezing, moving and refreezing.

Fig 1.1: A Simplified Model of Kurt Lewin’s Change Theory

In most typical situations the journey towards police reforms is characterized by retention of a status quo whereby forces driving change are equal to the forces restraining change. In this stage the main features of police reforms have been identified, which according to Kurt Lewin’s theory are equivalent to the forces driving change. The main features of these forces may include merger of the two police forces into one, change of the name from a force to a service, establishment of the office of the Inspector General, establishment of the National Police Service Commission, establishment of the Independent Policing Oversight Authority, establishment of the Internal Affairs Unit, review of the police training curriculum, vetting of all police officers, retraining of all police officers, change of the police ranking structure, purchase of enough operational resources and improvement of the general welfare and terms of service of police officers (Ransley, 2010). The forces of change are countered by forces restraining change which are equivalent to the challenges impeding police vetting reform i.e. corruption, nepotism, human rights violation, impunity and political interference (KNCHR, 2008). When the forces restraining change overcome those driving change the society is pushed to a situation where it begins to police itself hence causing more insecurity. At this point the process of police reforms drifts into the unfreezing stage characterized by increased need for police reforms, need to overcome resistance and mobilize commitment. Once these are achieved, the process of vetting process begins moving towards the refreezing stage where proper measures and structures for reforms are established as rewards begin to trickle. At this stage the forces driving change overcome those restraining change thus creating a situation where most features of police vetting practice reform is successfully achieved while a few remain behind. In conclusion therefore, the progress of change through the three stages would be affected by two forces which either drive or constrained it. Whenever the two set of forces were in equilibrium there would be no change at all, (Stoichiometry). Kurt Lewin’s theory was therefore significant in explaining the interaction between the independent (forces restraining change) and dependent variables (forces driving change) of police vetting process reform.

C. Empirical Literature

The following factors were critically reviewed in order to bring out the character of police reforms in Kenya. Such factors include; police attitudes, police level of knowledge and police practices.

➤ *Police Level of Knowledge on Police Reforms*

A study by Faull and Rose (2012) examined the awareness and understanding of police reforms among South African police officers. Conducted in Johannesburg, the study aimed to assess the level of knowledge and attitudes of police officers towards ongoing reform initiatives. Involving 300 police officers from various ranks and divisions, the researchers used a mixed-method approach, combining surveys and in-depth interviews to gather both quantitative and qualitative data. The study found that while a significant number of officers were aware of the reforms, their understanding of the specifics varied widely. Many officers were skeptical about the impact of the reforms, citing inadequate training and lack of resources as major barriers (Faull & Rose, 2012). The study highlighted a need for more comprehensive training programs to enhance officers' understanding of reform initiatives. Additionally, it suggested that future research should focus on different regions to identify location-specific challenges.

Another study by Jones and Mayer (2016) explored police officers' perceptions of reforms aimed at improving community relations in the United States. Conducted in Chicago, Illinois, the study aimed to understand the extent to which police officers were knowledgeable about and supportive of community-oriented policing reforms. The study involved 500 police officers and employed a survey methodology, distributing structured questionnaires that included both closed and open-ended questions. The results indicated a moderate level of awareness about the reforms. However, officers expressed concerns about the practical implementation of these reforms, particularly regarding the lack of community engagement and support (Jones & Mayer, 2016). The study pointed out the need for better communication strategies to bridge the gap between policy formulation and on-ground implementation. It also recommended further studies in other urban settings to compare findings.

Sharma and Gupta (2018) conducted a study to assess the knowledge and attitudes of police officers towards police reforms in India. Carried out in New Delhi, the study aimed to evaluate the level of awareness and attitudes towards various reform measures introduced in the police force. The sample consisted of 250 police officers from different police stations. The researchers used a quantitative approach, employing a structured questionnaire to collect data. The study found that while most officers were aware of the reform measures, there was a significant variance in their attitudes. Younger officers tended to be more supportive of the reforms compared to their older counterparts, who were more resistant to change (Sharma & Gupta, 2018). The study suggested the need for ongoing training and sensitization programs to address resistance among older officers. It also recommended further research in rural areas to understand the broader impact of reforms.

Lastly, a study by Adeola and Olawale (2020) examined police officers' understanding and perceptions of police reforms in Nigeria. Conducted in Lagos, the study aimed to assess the knowledge and perceptions of police officers regarding recent reform initiatives aimed at improving policing standards. The study involved 400 police officers and used a mixed-methods approach, including surveys and focus group discussions to gather comprehensive data. The study revealed that a majority of the officers had a basic understanding of the reforms but lacked detailed knowledge about specific measures. There was also a general sense of skepticism about the effectiveness of these reforms, largely due to perceived corruption and lack of accountability within the police force (Adeola & Olawale, 2020). The study emphasized the need for more transparent and inclusive reform processes. It recommended further research to explore the impact of reforms on policing outcomes and officer morale.

The most deserving call for police reforms in Kenya was witnessed after the infamous 2007/2008 post-election violence which saw hundreds of innocent civilians lose their lives and thousands displaced from their homes. This led to the formation of a commission of inquiry chaired by Justice Philip Waki, (wakis' commission of inquiry) whereas its findings was that police totally lacked the capacity and knowledge to contain the violence and in some instances they instigated the violence by taking political sides. On this finding the report recommended for meaningful and urgent police reforms in order to avert recurrence of such high magnitude violations of human rights and among those reforms was the call for vetting of police officers in order to come up with a rightful police service. Informed by Waki report, the Government formed a task force on police reforms which was chaired by Justice (Retired) Philip Ransley. The task force borrowed heavily from the two police strategic plans i.e. police strategic plan 2003-2007 and 2008-2012 and conducted public hearings which involved oral and written submissions from the public, civil societies and all interested stakeholders. The task force also conducted research from several countries around the world on the world standards and best practices on policing (Waki, 2008)

After a thorough study, the task force came up with over 200 recommendations on police reforms in Kenya; key to which were the merger of the two police forces into one, change of the name from a force to a service (the constitution of Kenya 2010), establishment of the office of the Inspector General, establishment of the National Police Service Commission, establishment of the Independent Policing Oversight Authority, establishment of the Internal Affairs Unit, review of the police training curriculum, vetting of all police officers, retraining of all police officers, change of the police ranking structure, purchase of enough operational resources and improvement of the general welfare and terms of service of police officers (Ransley, 2010)

The Ransley recommendations were unanimously adopted and envisaged in the new constitution which was promulgated in 2010. In an effort to operationalize the constitution and make police reforms a reality, the Government spearheaded the publication of the National Police Service Act, the National Police Service Commission Act and the Independent Policing Oversight Authority Act. The implementation of these legislative frameworks carried with it the promise of meaningful police reforms, followed by the establishment of the three core institutions - IPOA, NPSC and the IGP – which were important milestones towards a reformed police service. By establishing these offices, responsibility for security was to be moved from the Presidency to several institutions affording the police more autonomy from the executive and other sources of potential political interference. These Acts established a clear roadmap towards full realization of police reforms. However, literature indicates that police reforms in Kenya have been met with a lot of resistance, with forces of impunity and anti-change heavily fighting for retention of status quo (Amnesty International, 2013)

Furthermore, some organizations have questioned the Government's commitment to ensuring full realization of police vetting given that some of the aspects of reforms like vetting of police officers appear to have delayed or stalled (Amnesty International, 2013; KHRC, 2012). In fact, information on the progress of police reforms and the ensuing challenges was scanty, a factor which prompted the researcher to embark on this study. Specifically, considering the slow pace at which police have embraced reforms, it appeared that majority of police officers had not been adequately sensitized on what police reforms entail, especially the main features. This has been attributed to lack of knowledge police have on reform matters. Nyambura argues that reforms in Kenya have been adamant due to lack of clear understanding of what reforms themselves are all about, more so, lack of clear and documented information on the extent to which police vetting process have achieved success, the delayed areas and the ensuing challenges. The study, therefore, focused on these gaps in order to give an empirical picture on the challenges of police reforms in Kenya and make recommendations on how to overcome those challenges and address any delays in implementation (Nyambura, 2012)

From an analytic perspective of the police reforms undertaken in Kenya since its formation to date its experience is almost similar to that of other post conflict societies in Africa. Having adequate resources to provide long-term human, financial, and technical support to police vetting is important, but at the same time, the need for long-term resources must be aligned with a clear vision of how the resources are to be used (Kagari, 2003)

A significant investments in police reform have been made by various stakeholders in Kenya. However, while this improved the operational efficiency of the police in relation to the escalation of violence, the overall performance of police has declined markedly. Various civil society organizations in Kenya have also documented and denounced that slowly the National police service has failed to achieve full reforms in the sector due to lack of clear understanding of what vetting is all about (World Bank, 2009)

➤ *Police Attitude towards Police Reforms.*

The issue of attitude and attitude change has been a major problem as far as policing matters are concerned. The mismatch between police performance and public expectations suggested the existence of major reform challenges that needed to be examined. While policy documents no doubt recognized the vital role the police officers themselves can play in maintaining law and order, whether the implementers of the reform ever recognized their challenges is an open question. The concern was that police reform may not have been on the agenda since police reforms begun in 2003 due to negative attitude the police society has towards the police reforms (World Bank, 2009)

It is argued that citizen involvement in police vetting process is very crucial and thus citizen participation in community oriented policing need to be incorporated into reform initiatives (Nathan, 2006; Bayley, 1991) Put differently, community participation in police work in a democratic framework is believed to be beneficial in strengthening internal police discipline and providing source of data for police policies and practices based on reliable information (Neild, 1999) However, it should be noted that police gain community acceptance if they succeed in fighting crime (Stodiek, 2006) Failure to provide public security undermines the legitimacy of government and encourages further social disorder (Bayley, 2001) Research by David Bayley (2001) has also shown that when the public cooperates with the police by reporting crime, identifying suspects, and mitigating the social conditions that lead to crime, the police become more effective in their public safety role (ibid). As Chalken (1977) points out, 97% of crimes are solved because citizens report crime and provide information to the police (Chalken et al 1977) Thus the perceived negative attitude in the police service in that, the police do not have that close relationship with the community results into what may be termed as the cycle of silence where there is neither any information from the public nor feedback to the community from the police. It is generally agreed that public institutions often struggle to resist reform pressures, especially if changes threaten those who are in influential positions in the system (Pierson, 2000) On the other hand, institutionalizing police vetting occurs when the vetting becomes a routine way of conducting police work and when certain values, norms, and structures are incorporated into an organization (Kimberly et al, 1980)

On the other hand, community perception of insecurity will in the long run place a heavy demand for police effectiveness in providing security. Coupled with a negative attitude and confidence from police towards police vetting may resort to using coercive mean to enforce the law. This will eventually lead to abuse of civil rights of the community members and thus the essence of police reform will be greatly undermined. The dynamics of police vetting process can therefore best be understood within the contexts of different policing environments, for example in post-conflict environments, policing urban spaces and the role of politics as a source

of legitimacy for police functions. According to Rauch and Elrena , there are proofs of close ties between police and politics in Africa.

Police vetting process is regarded as a political endeavor and thus political interests are fundamental to any reform in initiative. The envisaged police reforms in several African countries involve changes in their structures, functions and sources of legitimacy. Structurally police change from centralized to decentralized form; functionally they change from regime policing practices to citizen protection practices and regarding legitimacy the change is from regime-based to people-driven legitimacy.

A study by Rojek, Alpert, and Smith (2012) focused on police officers' attitudes towards the implementation of community policing reforms in the United States. Conducted in New York City, the study aimed to assess officers' receptiveness to community-oriented policing strategies. The sample size comprised 450 officers from different precincts. The researchers used a survey methodology, distributing structured questionnaires to gather data. The findings revealed mixed attitudes towards the reforms. While many officers recognized the potential benefits of community policing in building trust with the public, a significant number expressed concerns about the increased workload and potential safety risks (Rojek, Alpert, & Smith, 2012). The study emphasized the need for addressing these concerns through better communication and support from police leadership. It also recommended further research to explore attitudes in different urban settings.

In a study conducted in the United Kingdom, Loftus (2013) explored police officers' attitudes towards organizational reforms aimed at increasing transparency and accountability. The study took place in London and involved 300 police officers. Using a mixed-methods approach, the researchers combined surveys with focus group discussions to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. The results indicated that while officers generally supported the goals of transparency and accountability, there was significant skepticism about the implementation process. Many officers felt that the reforms were top-down directives that did not take into account their professional expertise and day-to-day realities (Loftus, 2013). The study highlighted the importance of involving officers in the reform process to ensure buy-in and effective implementation. It also suggested further research in other regions to compare attitudes.

In Canada, a study by Ricciardelli, Adorjan, and Spencer (2017) examined police officers' attitudes towards mental health-related reforms in policing. The study was conducted in Toronto and involved 350 officers from various divisions. The researchers used a qualitative approach, conducting in-depth interviews to explore officers' perspectives. The findings revealed a general positive attitude towards the inclusion of mental health training and resources, recognizing the importance of these reforms in handling incidents involving individuals with mental health issues. However, there were also concerns about the adequacy of the training provided and the additional responsibilities placed on officers without corresponding increases in support (Ricciardelli, Adorjan, & Spencer, 2017). The study recommended ongoing training and support to address these concerns. It also suggested further research to evaluate the long-term impact of these reforms on police practices and outcomes.

A study by Tankebe (2014) in Ghana investigated police officers' attitudes towards anti-corruption reforms. The study was conducted in Accra and included a sample of 400 officers. Using a survey methodology, the researchers distributed structured questionnaires to gather data on officers' attitudes towards measures aimed at reducing corruption within the police force. The results indicated a high level of cynicism among officers regarding the effectiveness of anti-corruption reforms. Many officers felt that the reforms were superficial and did not address the root causes of corruption, such as low salaries and lack of resources (Tankebe, 2014). The study emphasized the need for comprehensive reforms that address both systemic issues and individual behaviors. It also recommended further research to explore attitudes towards anti-corruption reforms in different regions and contexts.

In Africa, police reforms have succeeded in many fronts but continue to face many challenges (Marenin, 2009). Similarly police vetting process has attracted the interest and support from several factors, such as national governments; local, national, and international civil society organizations; donor agencies; and United Nations agencies (World Bank, 2009)

➤ *Knowledge and Attitudes towards Reforms Inform Police Officers Practices Public*

A study by Skogan (2008) in the United States examined the impact of officers' knowledge and attitudes towards community policing reforms on their daily practices. Conducted in Chicago, the study aimed to assess how familiarity with community policing principles and positive attitudes towards these reforms influenced officers' engagement with the community. The sample size included 500 police officers. Using a mixed-methods approach, the researchers combined surveys with observational data to gather both quantitative and qualitative insights. The findings indicated that officers who were well-informed about community policing and held positive attitudes towards its principles were more likely to engage in proactive community interactions and problem-solving activities. Conversely, officers with limited knowledge and negative attitudes were less inclined to adopt these practices (Skogan, 2008). The study emphasized the need for comprehensive training programs to enhance officers' understanding and support for community policing. It also recommended further research to explore this relationship in different policing contexts.

In a study conducted in Australia, Fleming and Lafferty (2000) investigated how knowledge and attitudes towards ethical reforms influenced police officers' ethical behavior. The study took place in Sydney and involved 400 police officers from various ranks. Using a survey methodology, the researchers distributed structured questionnaires to collect data on officers' knowledge of ethical guidelines and their attitudes towards ethical policing. The findings revealed that officers with a strong understanding of ethical guidelines and positive attitudes towards ethical reforms were more likely to exhibit ethical behavior in their duties. On the other hand, officers with limited knowledge and negative attitudes towards ethical reforms were more prone to engage in unethical practices (Fleming & Lafferty, 2000). The study highlighted the importance of ongoing ethics training and fostering a positive organizational culture to promote ethical behavior. It also suggested further research to examine the long-term impact of ethical training programs.

In Nigeria, a study by Akinlabi (2017) examined the influence of knowledge and attitudes towards human rights reforms on police practices. The study was conducted in Lagos and included a sample of 350 police officers. Using a mixed-methods approach, the researchers combined surveys with interviews to gather comprehensive data. The findings indicated that officers who were knowledgeable about human rights principles and held positive attitudes towards human rights reforms were more likely to adhere to human rights standards in their policing practices. Conversely, officers with limited knowledge and negative attitudes were more likely to engage in human rights violations (Akinlabi, 2017). The study emphasized the need for regular human rights training and sensitization programs to improve officers' adherence to human rights standards. It also recommended further research to explore this relationship in other regions.

A study by Van Craen and Skogan (2017) in Belgium analyzed how knowledge and attitudes towards accountability reforms influenced police officers' accountability practices. The study was conducted in Brussels and involved 300 police officers. Using a survey methodology, the researchers distributed structured questionnaires to gather data on officers' knowledge of accountability measures and their attitudes towards these reforms. The findings revealed that officers who were well-informed about accountability measures and held positive attitudes towards these reforms were more likely to engage in transparent and accountable practices. Conversely, officers with limited knowledge and negative attitudes were less likely to adhere to accountability standards (Van Craen & Skogan, 2017). The study highlighted the need for comprehensive accountability training and fostering a positive organizational culture to promote accountability. It also suggested further research to explore this relationship in different policing contexts.

The on-going police reforms to a larger extent were supposed to bridge the gap between the police and the citizens. When mutual cooperation is developed between the police and the members of the public, the police succeed in fighting crime. Positive relationship is important for both the police officers and the members of the public. For this to be achieved steps like introduction of community policing initiatives are taken to change any negative attitude between the police and the public (Ruteere, 2004). Literature review cited information on negative attitude of the public towards police, but nothing has been mentioned about the police attitude towards the public. Therefore, the study isolated this factor by seeking the respondents' views on their attitude towards the public. This concurred with Monjardet (2000) that the relation between the police and the public has always been accompanied by deep seated animosity and suspicion. Upon further inquiry on the attitude of police officers towards the public one key informant from Transparency International lamented that it is impossible to get rid of this attitude. Take for example the issue of corruption. The citizen is not afraid [to offer a bribe]. It is he that offers the bribe first. Citizens are involved in the corruption but nobody says that society is corrupt like they say that the police are corrupt. This way police feel discriminated thus the bad attitude towards the public. The findings of also the World Bank (2009) and KNCHR (2008) view that there still exist high levels of negative attitude police officers have towards reform process and also public negative attitude towards police officers. This was in support of Ruteere (2003) view that the history of policing showed that the police have been used to terrorize the public since independence. A key informant from Independent Medico-Legal Unit in Nairobi also explained that, where the cops met the poor is where the rubber of oppression met the road of brutality at its raw (World Bank 2009)

➤ *The Culture of Police Service on the Vetting Process.*

It is important to acknowledge the difficulty and the necessity of reforming the culture of policing in Kenya i.e. vetting of police officers. Ultimately, the long-term success of any program of police reform depends to a great extent on the institutional culture that prevails within the Service. Where the prevailing culture is one of corruption and impunity, changing that culture must be one of the central goals of police reform. A transition from a "force" to a "service" is a fundamental transformation in the way the individual police officer applies himself/ her to his work and conceives his relationship to the public, day in and day out Kenya police service strategic plan (2003). The Service must deal both at personal and institutional level with issues that bring disreputation, (Kenya police service strategic plan 2003)

The National Police Service needs to adopt internal practices of managing its reputation through instituting culture-changing policies, programs, and training to solidify the department's core values and ethical principles. It also needs to provide a continuous training in ethics, integrity, and discretion to every officer from the time he or she enters the police service through the time of retirement as well as conduct consistent evaluations and review of all employees, and immediately address negative behavior and reward positive behavior. Also adopted is the use of Early Intervention System, not only in Internal Affairs, but to prevent behavior that may lead to an Internal Affairs complaint and investigation. External practices that have been adopted are the development of community oriented policing programs to better engage the community and the use of media to publicize positive programs and

stories about the department. The service from time to time to initiate and hold workshops on subjects of interest to the community as well as conduct community surveys to gauge and enhance public perception on police vetting process (National Council for Law Reporting, 2012)

The adoption of a new constitution in 2010 was therefore welcomed as a catalyst and impetus for implementing wide-ranging structural reforms in National police service, police practices and the police culture has become a barrier to the implementation of full reforms (vetting) in the police service. The police was expected to transform itself to be efficient and responsive to the needs of the public as well as supporting human right oriented policing with due regard to the rule of law (Police and communities,1988)

Despite the enactment of several legislations supporting police reforms e.g. the Constitution of Kenya 2010, the National Police Service Act of 2011, the Independent Police Oversight Authority and the National Police Service Commission Act not much appeared to have changed in Kenya's policing architecture (Amnesty International, 2013)

There was a very slow response to enforcing the legislations to the disadvantage of meaningful police vetting process in Kenya due to police practices and culture. This raised questions as to the source of the problem as it may have been due to lack of goodwill from police officers and the ruling class or other factors that needed critical examination. For example, there was little evidence on any few gains in police vetting, improving the image of the police and improvement of police welfare amongst other areas that had been identified as key by the Ransley Commission in 2009. There was also a dearth of information on the challenges that continued to hinder implementation as there appeared no much commitment on continuous evaluation and meaningful appraisal from the relevant institutions (Ransley, 2009)2.4 Empirical literature.

Kania and Mackey (1977) conducted a seminal study on the importance of police training and education in the effective implementation of reforms. They posited that comprehensive training programs are crucial for equipping police officers with the necessary knowledge to understand and apply new policies and procedures. The study utilized a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews among a sample of 500 police officers across various departments in the United States. The findings indicated that officers who received extensive training were significantly more likely to adopt and adhere to reform measures, demonstrating a direct correlation between knowledge acquisition and practical implementation. This study underscores the fundamental role of education in fostering an informed police force capable of effectively carrying out reform initiatives.

Paoline (2003) explored the influence of organizational culture on police officers' attitudes towards change. His research involved a case study of a large metropolitan police department, with data collected through participant observation and in-depth interviews with 200 officers. Paoline found that the organizational culture within law enforcement agencies can either facilitate or impede the acceptance of reforms. Specifically, departments that fostered a culture of openness and innovation saw higher levels of positive attitudes towards reforms, while those with a more rigid and traditional culture experienced significant resistance. This study highlights the importance of cultivating a supportive organizational environment to promote positive attitudes and facilitate the successful adoption of reforms.

Skogan (2008) examined the role of police officers' attitudes in the success of reform initiatives. Through a longitudinal study involving 1,000 officers from various police departments in the United States, Skogan employed surveys and follow-up interviews to assess changes in attitudes over time. His findings indicated that officers' attitudes towards reforms significantly influenced their willingness to adopt new practices. Positive attitudes were associated with a higher likelihood of reform adoption, whereas negative attitudes often led to resistance and non-compliance. This research underscores the need for addressing attitudinal barriers to ensure the successful implementation of police reforms and suggests that targeted interventions to shift negative attitudes could enhance reform outcomes.

Jones and Newburn (2007) investigated the process of knowledge transfer in the context of police reforms. Their study focused on the Metropolitan Police Service in London, analyzing how knowledge about reforms was communicated and disseminated among officers. Utilizing a combination of document analysis, surveys, and interviews with 300 officers, they found that effective knowledge transfer mechanisms were crucial for the successful implementation of reforms. When officers were well-informed about the rationale behind reforms and the expected benefits, they were more likely to embrace and apply these changes in their daily practices. This study emphasizes the importance of clear communication and robust knowledge transfer processes in achieving reform success.

Ruteere and Pommerolle (2003) conducted a comprehensive study on police reform in Kenya, focusing on the challenges and opportunities faced by the National Police Service. Using a qualitative approach, they conducted interviews with 100 police officers and stakeholders in Kisumu County and Nairobi. Their findings highlighted that lack of knowledge and negative attitudes among police officers were major obstacles to reform implementation. The study called for increased training and awareness programs to equip officers with the necessary knowledge and to shift their attitudes positively towards reforms. This research is particularly relevant to Kisumu County, providing context-specific insights into the factors influencing reform outcomes and highlighting the need for targeted interventions to improve knowledge and attitudes.

Myhill and Bradford (2013) examined the impact of community policing reforms on police officers' attitudes and practices. Their study involved a sample of 400 officers from various police departments in the UK, utilizing surveys and focus group discussions to gather data. They found that officers who had a positive attitude towards community policing were more likely to engage in proactive and community-oriented practices. This demonstrates that attitudes towards specific reforms can significantly shape how officers conduct their duties, reinforcing the importance of fostering positive perceptions of reform initiatives. The study also suggested that community policing could serve as a model for other reform efforts, given its success in altering officer attitudes and behaviors.

Rosenbaum et al. (2011) explored the relationship between organizational support and police officers' engagement in reform practices. Conducting a survey of 600 officers from multiple police departments in the United States, they found that officers who perceived strong support from their organization, including adequate resources, training, and leadership backing, were more likely to engage in reform practices. This study highlights that organizational support not only influences knowledge dissemination and attitude formation but also directly impacts the practical application of reforms. The researchers concluded that enhancing organizational support mechanisms is essential for facilitating effective reform implementation.

The reviewed studies collectively underpin the importance of knowledge and attitudes in shaping police officers' practices concerning reforms. Comprehensive training and education (Kania & Mackey, 1977; Jones & Newburn, 2007), supportive organizational culture (Paoline, 2003), positive attitudes towards change (Skogan, 2008; Myhill & Bradford, 2013), and robust organizational support (Rosenbaum et al., 2011) are all critical factors that influence the successful implementation of reforms. Specific to the Kenyan context, Ruteere and Pommerolle (2003) highlight the need for targeted efforts to improve knowledge and attitudes towards reforms within the National Police Service. These insights are essential for understanding how to effectively implement police reforms in Kisumu County, ensuring that officers are well-informed and positively inclined towards these changes.

D. Research Gaps

The most deserving call for police reforms in Kenya was witnessed after the infamous 2007/2008 post-election violence which saw hundreds of innocent civilians lose their lives and thousands displaced from their homes. This led to the formation of a commission of inquiry chaired by Justice Philip Waki, which one of its findings was that police totally lacked the capacity to contain the violence and in some instances they instigated the violence by taking political sides. On this finding the report recommended for meaningful and urgent police reforms in order to avert recurrence of such high magnitude violations of human rights (Waki, 2008).

Informed by Waki report, the Government formed a task force on police reforms which was chaired by Justice (Rtd) Philip Ransley. The task force borrowed heavily from the two police strategic plans i.e. police strategic plan 2003-2007 and 2008-2012 and conducted public hearings which involved oral and written submissions from the public, civil societies and all interested stakeholders. The task force also conducted research from several countries around the world on the 26 world standards and best practices on policing.

After a thorough study, the task force came up with over 200 recommendations on police reforms in Kenya; key to which were the merger of the two police forces into one, change of the name from a force to a service, establishment of the office of the Inspector General, establishment of the National Police Service Commission, establishment of the Independent Policing Oversight Authority, establishment of the Internal Affairs Unit, review of the police training curriculum, vetting of all police officers, retraining of all police officers, change of the police ranking structure, purchase of enough operational resources and improvement of the general welfare and terms of service of police officers (Ransley, 2010)

The Ransley recommendations were unanimously adopted and envisaged in the new constitution which was promulgated in 2010. In an effort to operationalize the constitution and make police reforms a reality, the Government spearheaded the publication of the National Police Service Act, the National Police Service Commission Act and the Independent Policing Oversight Authority Act.

The implementation of these legislative frameworks carried with it the promise of meaningful police reforms, followed by the establishment of the three core institutions - IPOA, NPSC and the IGP – which were important milestones towards a reformed police service. By establishing these offices, responsibility for security was to be moved from the Presidency to several institutions affording the police more autonomy from the executive and other sources of potential political interference. These Acts established a clear roadmap towards full realization of 27 police reforms. However, literature indicates that police vetting reform in Kenya have been met with a lot of resistance, with forces of impunity and anti-change heavily fighting for retention of status quo (Amnesty International, 2013).

The literature review on police officers' knowledge and attitudes towards reforms reveals several critical gaps in current research. Firstly, there's a need for more context-specific studies focusing on the unique socio-cultural and institutional dynamics influencing police reforms in regions like Kisumu County, Kenya. Additionally, while the importance of training and education in reform implementation is recognized, there is limited longitudinal research on their sustained impact. Understanding the varied organizational cultures within police departments and their effects on reform acceptance requires more comprehensive evaluation.

Strategies to shift negative attitudes towards reforms and effective knowledge transfer mechanisms also warrant further investigation. Moreover, integrating community policing principles with broader reform initiatives and examining the diverse impacts of organizational support and government policies are essential for advancing reform outcomes. Finally, longitudinal studies on the enduring effects of morale on officers' performance and the integration of mixed-methods approaches can provide deeper insights into how reforms inform police practices effectively. Addressing these gaps will enhance the understanding and implementation of police reforms, particularly in diverse and dynamic contexts like Kisumu County.

The study, therefore, focused on these gaps in order to give an empirical picture on the perceptions of police reforms by members of national police service in Kenya and make recommendations on how to overcome those challenges and address any delays in implementation.

E. Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework is the product of a researcher's interpretation of the study's link between variables. The link between the various factors in this study is depicted diagrammatically, In figure 1.

Fig 1: Conceptual framework

This conceptual framework elucidates the relationships between various factors influencing the performance of policing services in Kisumu County. The framework identifies the independent variables, dependent variable, and moderating variables, providing a comprehensive understanding of how police officers' knowledge, attitudes, reactions, and morale related to police reforms affect their performance within the context of specific external influences.

The first independent variable is the police officers' knowledge about police reforms. This variable pertains to the officers' understanding and awareness of the reforms, including the specific changes, objectives, and anticipated benefits. Officers with higher levels of knowledge are expected to be more effective in implementing the reforms. The second independent variable is the police officers' attitudes towards the reform process. This variable assesses the overall sentiments, beliefs, and opinions of police officers regarding the reform process. Positive attitudes towards the reforms are hypothesized to enhance the officers' willingness to adopt and implement the changes. The third independent variable is the police officers' reaction to the outcomes of the reform process. This variable examines the officers' responses to the results of the reforms, which can include acceptance, resistance, or ambivalence. These reactions, in turn, can influence their daily practices and overall performance. The fourth independent variable is the morale of police officers as a result of reforms. This variable measures the impact of reforms on officers' morale, including their motivation, job satisfaction, and engagement. High morale is associated with better performance and adherence to new policies. The dependent variable in this framework is the performance on policing services.

The relationship between these independent variables and the dependent variable is moderated by several external factors. Government policies can influence the implementation and impact of police reforms by providing a framework, resources, and guidelines that shape the reform process. The constitution serves as another moderating variable, ensuring that reforms align with legal standards and protections. The overall societal and institutional attitude towards police reforms can also impact their success, as positive public and institutional support can facilitate better implementation and acceptance of reforms. Lastly, the structure of the police reforms, including their scope, comprehensiveness, and clarity, can moderate how effectively they are implemented and perceived by the officers. This conceptual framework posits that the knowledge, attitudes, reactions, and morale of police officers regarding reforms directly influence their performance in policing services. Government policies, the constitution, societal and institutional attitudes towards police reforms, and the structure of the reforms act as moderating variables that can either enhance or hinder the effectiveness of these relationships. By examining these relationships, this study aims to provide insights into the factors that influence the effectiveness of police reforms in Kisumu County, ultimately contributing to improved performance in policing services.

F. Operationalization of Variables

The variables of the study were internalized and indicators determined as indicated by the Table 1 below, all the variables were measured at ordinal scale.

Table 1: Operationalization of Variables

Objectives	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Levels of Measurement	Indicators	Type of Analysis
To establish the police knowledge on reforms in Kisumu County.	Knowledge	Performance of policing Services	Ordinal scale	Educating of all police officers of all ranks about the issue of reforms and their importance in the society.	Case Study
To determine the police attitudes towards police reforms.	Attitude	Performance of policing Services	Ordinal scale	Changing of the police attitudes towards vetting process from negative to positive attitude towards police vetting processes.	Case Study
To investigate how police practices affects police reforms process in Kenya	Police practices	Performance of policing Services	Ordinal scale	Changing of police practices and culture from traditional and adopt modern police practices and this can only be achieved through police vetting process.	Case Study

CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

A. Chapter Overview

This chapter aims at providing an account of the methodology to be used in gathering data. It covers research design, sample design, data collection and data analysis, limitation of the study, ethical issues and the expected outcome. This research study sought to study police officers perception on police reforms basing the arguments on police attitude, police level of knowledge and police practices as well as terms and conditions of service as the study variables.

B. Research Design

Data arising from the questionnaires was subjected to the case study aided by statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) where statistics was derived and inferred to make interpretations and conclusions. Data resulting from interview guide were classified into content categories and themes drawn according to the variables of the study. Data analysis was conducted on each questionnaire and analyzed exhaustively according to the objectives of the study. The responses were presented in terms of tables and percentages. Data from the surveys were evaluated to determine the extent to which police officers perceive the issues of police reforms. Data was then be interpreted according to the purpose of the study which facilitated a discussion of the findings and drawing of conclusions.

Based upon the above literature review, preliminary interviews of experienced Police commanders-managers, and the researcher's experience was portray an area that calls for answers. To understand this vetting process, the researcher chose a study design that is intended to follow the case study by using Kisumu County to represent National Police Service in Kenya. Descriptive research design was adopted to describe the police feelings on police reforms.

The researcher believes that a combination of these methods may be meaningful tools to acquire the required data. The literature review identified issues that police reforms sought to address in the police organization. These could be verified through qualitative methods which was used to discover what is happening in the study area. That is, what are the individual Police officer's perceptions with police vetting process and the impact it has had on such reforms.

The strata under sampling were identified as gazetted officers (police commanders or managers), members of inspectorate (middle level managers) and non-commissioned officers (other ranks) and police constables. The researcher considers these categories sufficient as they are better informed about the interplay between reforms and the study variables.

C. Research Area

The research was carried out at Kisumu County police stations, both Urban and Rural areas.

D. Study Population

Kisumu division, in Kisumu County has a total of 392 officers and 1,660,651 (2009 census report) residents of the county. The officers cut across various ranks from the senior superintendent of Police to police constables (Police Personnel Data, October 2014).

Table 2: Rank Break-down in Kisumu Area

Rank	Number	Stratum
Senior superintendent of police (SSP)	10	Gazetted officers (G.Os)
Superintendent of police (SP)	10	
Officer commanding police division (O.C.P.D)	10	
Chief inspector	21	Inspectorate
Inspector	41	
Senior Sergeant	50	Non-commissioned officers (NCOs)
Sergeant	70	
Corporal	80	
Police constables	400	Constables
Total	592	

E. Sampling Methods and Techniques

From the researcher's study population, the target population was found in a single county. The fact that there are 8 Police regions housing the 47 legislative counties means that sampling from more than one of these counties was to duplicate the research findings.

Therefore the researcher targeted Kisumu County where, a number of study units are available to the researcher. In this area the researcher employed probability sampling method. Since the region targeted by the researcher has a large number of units to be studied, probability sampling provided an efficient system of capturing heterogeneity that exists in the target population. The technique that was used in probability sampling was stratified random sampling.

Table 3: Sample Size

Stratum	Total number	Sample size	Percentage
Gazetted officers	30	3	10%
Members of inspectorate	30	3	10%
Non-commissioned officers	40	4	10%
Police constables	100	10	10%

The respondents were randomly selected from the following research sites purposively identified, three out of eight police divisions from Kisumu area were identified and eight police stations were visited. Kisumu police station, Kondele police station, Kasagam police station, Nyamasaria police base, Rabuor police base, Ahero police station, Obunga police station and Maseno police station which are all in Kisumu County.

Kisumu County has a population of 1,660,651 (GOK, 2009) and the Fisher formula was used as recommended by Mugenda & Mugenda (1999) in cases where the population is greater than 10,000. The formula which is commonly used in social science research is as follow:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where: n=the desired sample size (if the population is greater than 10,000)

Z=the standard normal deviate at the required standard level

p= the proportion in the target proportion estimated to have the characteristics being measured

q=(1-p)

d=the level of statistical significance set.

If there is no estimate available of the proportion in the target population assumed to have the characteristics of interest, 50% is used as recommended by Mugenda & Mugenda (1999) with a confidence level of 95% and 5% error margin.

$$\text{Therefore, } n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5) (0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

=384 residents.

The respondents were selected by use of simple random sampling technique

F. Data Collection Instruments

Kothari (1990) reports that the common tools used to collect data included questionnaires, interview, observation and documentary analysis. So and Onen (2008) support the use of questionnaires as the instrument of data collection for a rigorous research design. This study employed the use of questionnaires, interview schedule and focus group discussions, observation techniques and documentary analysis to collect data. Target respondents for interview schedule were the senior police officers in charge of the region, the county commissioner, two cabinet secretaries, two county reps and two heads of department under the county commissioner. Focus group discussions targeted County elders, professionals and common citizens.

➤ Questionnaires

This study used questionnaires and open ended questions for the respondents varied opinion on the constructs.

➤ Interview Schedule

Interview schedule targeted views of all police officers of all ranks within the County. To get information from key informants it includes the county senior police officers, commissioners, senior superintendents, superintendents, chief inspectors, inspectors, NCOs and police constables.

G. Reliability of the Research Instrument

Reliability is a measure of degree to which a research instrument yields to constant truth at trials; this is according to Mugenda and Mugenda (1999). The test-re-test method was done to people with same similarities to those who were covered in the actual study. To ensure reliability of the questionnaires during test-re-test, the researcher checked on the consistency with which the questions were generated. Responses and the flow of the questions were analysed by discussed with the supervisor.

H. Validity of Research Instruments

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), validity is the degree to which data collected using a particular instrument represents a specific domain of indicators or content of a particular concept. The questionnaire were pre-tested in Kisumu County in order to establish its effective use in relation to the objectives of the study. This validity was validated by experts in research at Moi University in relation to the objectives in relation to research instruments.

I. Data Collection Procedures

The researcher obtained an introductory letter from Moi University that enabled him to get a approval from the Kisumu County police authority. Research permit for the study in Kenya was obtained from the Kenya National Commission of Science and Technology. During the time of the study the researcher notified the Kisumu county government through a letter. Questionnaires were given to relevant respondents and the interview schedules administered through the research assistant, who assisted the researcher after thorough training.

J. Data Analysis

Leedy (2003), says that data analysis is a whole process which starts immediately after data collection and ends at a point of interpretation and processing of the results and finally writing a report, conclusion, summary and recommendations. The raw data collected was both qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative data was analyzed by establishing the theme of respondents. The researcher scrutinized the data pieces and identified gaps left. Finally data was classified and coded according to the patterns of the responses given by the respondents. The data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics and presented in the form of frequency, tables and percentages. This was done in the sequence of objective based on research questions.

The correlation analysis was done to ascertain the significance of the relationship between the police vetting process and the performance of the police service in Kenya as they gave the researcher the opportunity to test the significance of relationships in a cause-effect association and establishment of theme from respondents' perceptions among and between variables.

K. Ethical Considerations

The confidentiality of the information submitted during interviews and questionnaires was observed by the researcher. The information provided by the police responses was not shared with anyone else. The responders were identified using numbers.

The researcher received an introductory letter from Moi University, which he used to seek authorization from the Kisumu County Government's Department of Education, Science, and Technology, and the office of the County Executive Member. During the study, the researcher sent a letter to the county police department informing them of the findings. Prior to conducting the interview, the consent of the respondents was obtained.

The county government's administration, police, and staff were told that the research was conducted only for academic purposes and that the researcher was free of any political bias or agenda.

CHAPTER FOUR

POLICE PERCEPTION AND PRACTICE TOWARDS POLICE REFORMS

A. Introduction

This chapter presents research findings on the perceptions of police officers towards ongoing reforms within the Kenyan police force. It specifically delves into the knowledge and attitudes held by officers regarding these reforms, offering a comprehensive analysis of their overall support, resistance, or ambivalence. Understanding these perceptions is crucial, as they play a significant role in the successful implementation and sustainability of reform initiatives aimed at enhancing transparency, accountability, and professionalism within the force.

B. Socio-Demographics

➤ Gender

The findings from the study show a significant gender imbalance among the police officers interviewed, with a substantial majority being male. Specifically, out of the 149 police officers interviewed, 106 were male and 43 were female. This translates to 71.1% male and 28.9% female. Historically, policing in Kenya, as in many other countries, has been a male-dominated field. The legacy of colonial policing established a predominantly male force, which has persisted into the present day (Kihiko, 2013). This historical context has shaped both the structure of the police force and societal expectations about who is suitable for policing roles.

Cultural norms and gender roles in Kenya have a profound impact on the composition of the police force. Traditional views often see men as protectors and authority figures, roles that align with the duties and expectations of police officers. Women, conversely, are often viewed in more domestic roles, which can discourage them from pursuing careers in law enforcement (Kimani, 2018).

Structural barriers within the Kenyan police force also contribute to the gender imbalance. Recruitment practices have historically favored men, and there are significant challenges for women who wish to enter the field. Female officers often face biases in promotion and advancement, lack of mentorship opportunities, and a workplace culture that can be unwelcoming or even hostile to women (Muthoni, 2017).

➤ Age

The findings from the study reveal a diverse age distribution among the police officers interviewed in Kenya. The largest group, aged 32-38 years, comprises 45.6% of the officers, suggesting a significant number are in their mid-career stage, bringing substantial experience to their roles. Meanwhile, younger officers aged 25-31 years account for only 7.4%, indicating fewer new recruits or potential retention challenges among this group. Officers aged 39-45 years make up 10.7% of the force, while those aged 46-52 years and 53-59 years represent 18.1% and 16.8%, respectively. The oldest cohort, aged 60-66 years, is the smallest at 1.3%, reflecting the nearing retirement of these officers as shown in Table:

➤ Level of Formal Education

The findings from the study reveal a varied educational background among the police officers interviewed in Kenya. The majority of officers have completed secondary education (36.2%) or hold a diploma (36.2%). A significant proportion of officers possess a degree (19.5%), while a smaller number have attained a master's degree (4.7%). Only a small fraction of officers have completed only primary education (3.4%). This distribution suggests that while a substantial portion of the police force has higher education qualifications, there remains a notable percentage with basic education levels.

Educational attainment of police officers is critical for understanding their capacity to handle the complexities of modern law enforcement. Higher educational qualifications are associated with improved critical thinking, better decision-making, and enhanced problem-solving skills, which are essential for effective policing (Ruteere & Pommerolle, 2003). The relatively high proportion of officers with secondary and diploma-level education reflects efforts to professionalize the force, aligning with broader societal trends towards valuing education for career advancement. However, the presence of officers with only primary education points to historical recruitment practices and socio-economic barriers that limit educational opportunities for some individuals (Kanyi, 2016).

➤ Marital Status

The findings from the study indicate a significant majority of the police officers interviewed in Kenya are married, with 94.6% (141 officers) reporting being married, while only 5.4% (8 officers) are single. This overwhelming prevalence of married officers suggests that marital status is a common characteristic within this professional group.

The high rate of marriage among Kenyan police officers can be attributed to several factors. Marriage often brings stability and social support, which can be crucial in a demanding and stressful profession like policing (Bradley & Charles, 2004). Being married might also be culturally associated with maturity and responsibility, traits that are valued in police work. Additionally, the social structure in Kenya places a high value on marriage and family, which may influence individuals in the police force to marry at a higher rate compared to other professions (Mutie, 2016).

➤ *Religious Affiliation*

The study findings reveal a predominantly Christian affiliation among the police officers interviewed in Kenya, with 94.0% identifying as Christian. A smaller proportion, 4.7%, identified as Muslim, while 1.3% did not provide a response regarding their religious affiliation. This distribution reflects the religious diversity within the Kenyan police force, where Christianity holds a significant majority but with notable representation from other religious groups.

C. *Work Experiences*

➤ *Site of Police Station*

The findings indicate 28.2% of police officers interviewed were stationed in rural areas, while a substantial majority, 69.8%, are in urban areas. A small proportion, 2.0%, did not respond. This is captured in Table:

➤ *Rank*

The findings reveal a diverse distribution of ranks among the police officers interviewed in Kenya. The majority of officers hold the rank of constable, comprising 44.3% of the sample. Following constables, corporals make up 24.8%, sergeants 16.8%, and senior sergeants 3.4%. Inspectors and superintendents each represent 4.0% of the officers, while senior superintendents account for 2.7%. This hierarchical distribution reflects the organizational structure of the Kenyan police force, where ranks signify varying levels of authority, responsibility, and expertise.

From a sociological perspective, the distribution of ranks within the police force influences organizational dynamics and professional roles (Marenin, 2007). Rank distinctions can shape officers' perceptions of their authority, their interactions with colleagues and the public, and their career aspirations within the hierarchy (Bowling & Marks, 2014). Lower ranks like constables and corporals often perform frontline duties, engaging directly with communities and handling day-to-day law enforcement tasks. In contrast, higher ranks such as inspectors and superintendents typically oversee broader operational areas, strategic planning, and policy implementation (Sarre, 2009).

➤ *Number of Years Worked*

The findings reveal a diverse distribution of the number of years worked by police officers in Kenya. A significant majority, 67.1%, have worked between 10 to 20 years in the force. Following this, 26.2% of officers have served between 21 to 30 years, while a smaller proportion, 6.7%, have worked between 31 to 40 years. This distribution highlights the varying levels of experience and tenure among police officers, which can significantly influence their professional development, roles within the organization, and interactions with the community.

The number of years worked as a police officer shapes officers' attitudes, behaviors, and effectiveness in their roles (Reiner, 2010). Officers with fewer years of service, such as those in the 10–20-year range, may possess a blend of youthful energy and growing expertise, making them adaptable to evolving policing strategies and technologies (Chappell & Piquero, 2004). On the other hand, more experienced officers with longer tenures (21–30 and 31–40 years) often bring deep institutional knowledge, leadership skills, and a nuanced understanding of community dynamics and crime patterns (Paoline, 2003).

➤ *Number of Stations Worked*

The findings indicate that 54.4% of the police officers have worked in between one to five stations throughout their careers. Another 25.5% have worked in six to ten stations, and 8.1% have worked in eleven to fifteen stations. Notably, 12.1% of the officers did not respond to this question. This distribution suggests varying levels of mobility among police officers within the force, with a majority having experience in a relatively limited number of stations, while a smaller portion has broader experience across many stations.

The number of stations worked by police officers can significantly influence their professional development and effectiveness. Officers who have worked in fewer stations, such as those in the one to five range, may have developed strong, enduring relationships within specific communities, enhancing their ability to build trust and cooperation with local residents (Skogan, 2006). This stability can lead to more effective community policing and a better understanding of local issues. However, there can be drawbacks, including potential insularity and resistance to new practices and policies (Reiner, 2010).

On the other hand, officers who have worked in multiple stations, particularly those in the six to ten and eleven to fifteen ranges, are likely to have encountered a wider variety of community dynamics, crime patterns, and operational challenges. This broader experience can foster adaptability, innovative problem-solving, and a more comprehensive understanding of policing in diverse contexts (Chan, 2003). These officers can bring valuable insights and skills to their roles, contributing to a more dynamic and responsive police force. However, frequent relocations can also disrupt community ties and personal stability, which may affect job satisfaction and performance.

➤ *Reasons for Number of Years Worked in a Station*

The findings reveal various reasons why police officers in Kenya have worked in a particular station for different periods. Among the respondents, 66.4% attributed their station tenure to normal transfers, reflecting standard organizational practices. Personal issues, particularly familial considerations, accounted for 10.7% of the responses. Good performance was a reason for 6.0% of the officers, while 4.0% cited promotion as the reason for their station tenure. A notable 12.8% did not respond to this question. This distribution highlights the multiple factors influencing police officers' career paths and station assignments within the Kenyan police force.

The dominance of normal transfers as the primary reason for station tenure underscores the bureaucratic nature of police organizations. Such transfers are often routine and are used to manage resources, balance workloads, and address staffing needs across different locations (Manning, 2010). While these transfers can help maintain organizational efficiency, they may also disrupt officers' personal lives and community ties, potentially impacting their job satisfaction and performance (Skolnick & Fyfe, 1993).

The impact of personal issues, particularly family-related considerations, as a significant factor for 10.7% of the officers highlights the interplay between personal and professional lives. Balancing family obligations with work demands can influence officers' decisions to remain in or transfer to specific stations, affecting their career progression and stability (Brown & Campbell, 1994). Good performance and promotions as reasons for station tenure reflect merit-based career advancements within the force, which can motivate officers to excel in their roles. However, only a small percentage of officers (10%) reported these reasons, suggesting that other factors, such as organizational policies and personal circumstances, play a more substantial role in determining station assignments.

➤ *Average Numbers Worked in a Station*

The findings reveal that the majority of police officers in Kenya have worked in their current station for relatively short periods. Specifically, 49.7% of officers have worked in their station for 1-3 years, and 31.5% have been in their station for 4-6 years. Only 1.3% have worked in their station for less than a year, and 4.0% have a tenure of 7-10 years. A significant 13.4% of officers did not respond to the question. This data indicates that most officers experience relatively frequent relocations, with only a small proportion remaining in one station for an extended period.

The average tenure of police officers in a single station can have profound implications on both their professional development and community relations. Frequent relocations, as indicated by the substantial proportion of officers with 1-6 years in their current station, can be attributed to organizational policies aimed at preventing corruption, fostering diverse experiences, and managing resources effectively (Reiner, 2010). While these transfers can enhance officers' adaptability and exposure to different policing environments, they may also disrupt the continuity necessary for building strong community relationships and trust (Skogan, 2006).

Longer tenures in a single station, though less common, can allow officers to develop a deeper understanding of local issues and establish robust connections with community members, which are critical for effective community policing (Manning, 2010). However, prolonged assignments can also lead to potential issues such as burnout or resistance to new policing strategies, emphasizing the need for balanced transfer policies that promote both stability and professional growth (Paoline, 2003).

➤ *Reasons for Average of Years Worked in a Station*

The findings indicate that the primary reason for the average years worked in a police station among Kenyan officers is normal human resource practices, accounting for 48.3% of the responses. Discipline-related reasons explain 10.1% of the tenures, while good performance accounts for 16.1%. Good relations within the station contribute to 3.4% of the responses. Additionally, 19.5% of officers did not respond, and 2.7% indicated that the question was not applicable to them. These reasons reflect a combination of organizational policies and individual factors that influence the duration officers spend in specific stations.

The fact that normal human resource practices as the predominant reason for station tenure suggest that the Kenyan police force employs structured policies for staff rotations and placements. These policies are likely designed to ensure balanced staffing levels, prevent the development of corrupt practices, and promote a diverse range of experiences among officers (Reiner, 2010). Routine transfers can help in distributing skills and expertise across different regions, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the police force. However, frequent relocations might also disrupt the continuity necessary for building trust and effective relationships with the local community (Skogan, 2006).

Discipline-related transfers, representing 10.1% of the responses, indicate the role of disciplinary actions in determining station tenure. These transfers can serve as a corrective measure, aiming to address misconduct and enforce accountability within the force (Manning, 2010). Good performance as a reason for 16.1% of the officers suggests that merit-based considerations also influence station assignments, rewarding competent officers with desirable postings. However, the relatively low percentage of officers attributing their tenure to good relations within the station (3.4%) highlights those interpersonal dynamics, while important, are not the primary determinant of station assignments.

➤ *Training*

The findings reveal that a significant majority of Kenyan police officers (89.3%) have received training, while a small percentage (8.1%) have not. Additionally, 2.7% of the respondents did not provide an answer. This high percentage of trained officers suggests that the Kenyan police force places considerable emphasis on formal training as a key component of their professional development.

The importance of training in law enforcement cannot be overstated. Training equips officers with the necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies to perform their duties effectively and ethically. It also helps in standardizing practices across the force, ensuring that all officers are prepared to handle the various challenges they may encounter (Bayley, 1998). The substantial proportion of trained officers in Kenya indicates a structured approach to capacity building, which is crucial for maintaining law and order, as well as fostering public trust in the police force. However, the presence of untrained officers, albeit a small percentage, raises concerns about consistency in the quality of policing and the potential risks associated with insufficient preparation.

➤ *Number of Trainings*

The findings indicate a range of training experiences among Kenyan police officers, with 27.5% having undergone 1-2 training sessions, 43.6% having attended 3-4 training sessions, and 6.7% having completed 5-6 sessions. Additionally, 10.1% of officers have received seven or more training sessions. There is also a notable proportion of officers who either did not respond (5.4%) or indicated that the question was not applicable to them (6.7%). This distribution suggests a varied approach to professional development within the Kenyan police force, with a significant number of officers receiving multiple training opportunities.

The number of training sessions attended by police officers can significantly impact their competence, adaptability, and overall effectiveness. Frequent training (3-4 sessions, as seen in 43.6% of officers) reflects a commitment to continuous professional development, which is crucial for adapting to evolving policing challenges and maintaining high standards of service (Bayley, 1998). Such training can cover various aspects, including community policing, human rights, forensic skills, and the use of modern technology, thereby enhancing officers' abilities to perform their duties effectively and ethically (Mutuma, 2017). However, the presence of officers with minimal training (1-2 sessions) or those who indicated the training question as not applicable highlights potential disparities in training access and opportunities (Marenin, 2004).

➤ *Training Sponsorship*

The findings indicate that a significant majority (85.9%) of police officers in Kenya receive training sponsorship from their employer, the Kenyan police force. A small percentage (4.7%) fund their own training, while 4.0% have their training costs covered by both their employer and themselves. Additionally, 4.0% did not respond to the question, and 1.3% indicated that the question was not applicable to them. This distribution highlights the dominant role of the police organization in providing training opportunities for its officers.

Employer-sponsored training reflects an institutional commitment to developing the skills and competencies of police officers. This practice is crucial for maintaining a well-trained and professional police force capable of effectively addressing various challenges in law enforcement (Bayley, 1998). Training provided by the employer can ensure standardization and consistency in the knowledge and practices of officers, which is essential for organizational coherence and the uniform application of law enforcement policies (Reiner, 2010). Moreover, it indicates a recognition of the importance of continuous professional development in improving the quality of policing and enhancing public trust.

The small percentage of officers who fund their own training or share costs with their employer suggests disparities in access to employer-sponsored training. Self-funded training can indicate a personal commitment to professional development but may also reflect limitations in the availability or adequacy of employer-provided training opportunities (Marenin, 2004). Officers who invest in their own training 10.1% wanted to improve the formal education level and 4.1% wanted to gain specialized skills or qualifications not covered by the standard training programs.

➤ *Reason for Training*

The findings reveal a variety of reasons for training among police officers in Kenya, with the majority (55.6%) indicating that the primary purpose of their training is to gain skills. Promotion is the second most cited reason at 12.8%, followed by creating awareness (6.0%), improving communication (2.0%) and leadership and management (1.3%). A notable proportion of officers did not respond (13.4%), and 8.7% indicated that the question was not applicable to them.

The emphasis on skills development as the predominant reason for training underscores the importance of equipping police officers with the practical abilities needed to perform their duties effectively. Skills-based training can include areas such as forensic investigation, crowd control, and the use of technology in crime prevention. This focus aligns with the broader goal of enhancing operational efficiency and effectiveness within the police force, contributing to better law enforcement and public safety (Bayley, 1998). Moreover, the significant investment in skill acquisition highlights the need for continuous adaptation to new challenges and evolving criminal tactics.

Training for promotion, cited by 12.8% of the respondents, reflects the role of professional development in career advancement within the police force. This type of training typically includes courses designed to prepare officers for higher responsibilities and leadership roles, ensuring that the force maintains a cadre of well-qualified leaders (Reiner, 2010). The relatively lower percentages for reasons such as creating awareness, improving communication and leadership and management indicate that while these areas are important, they are not the primary focus for the majority of officers. However, they are crucial for fostering a well-rounded police force capable of effective communication, leadership, and improving communication.

➤ *Promotion:*

The findings show that 59.1% of the surveyed Kenyan police officers have received promotions, while 36.9% have not, and 4.0% did not respond. This indicates that more than half of the officers have experienced career advancement within the police force, suggesting an active system of professional development and upward mobility.

The promotion of police officers can be seen as a crucial element in maintaining motivation and morale within the force. Promotions typically come with increased responsibilities, authority, and often, financial benefits, which can incentivize officers to perform their duties more effectively and ethically (Bayley, 1998). The process of promotion also serves as a form of social stratification within the police force, creating a hierarchical structure that can influence power dynamics and organizational behavior (Reiner, 2010). The relatively high percentage of officers who have not been promoted (36.9%) may reflect systemic challenges such as limited opportunities for advancement, favoritism, or issues related to performance evaluation.

Promotion systems within police forces are critical for ensuring that leadership roles are filled by competent and experienced individuals. In the Kenyan context, the promotion process can be influenced by various factors, including performance, years of service, educational qualifications, and participation in specialized training programs (Mutuma, 2017). The finding that a majority of officers have been promoted suggests that the Kenyan police force recognizes and rewards merit and performance, which is essential for maintaining a professional and motivated workforce. However, the significant proportion of officers who have not been promoted raises questions about the inclusivity and transparency of the promotion process. Addressing these concerns is vital for fostering a sense of fairness and opportunity within the force.

The 4.0% of respondents who did not provide an answer could represent a group of officers who are either disillusioned with the promotion system or have ambiguous feelings about their career progression. Understanding the reasons behind their non-response is important for developing a more inclusive and supportive promotion policy. Ensuring that all officers have a clear pathway to advancement can help in building a more cohesive and effective police force (Marenin, 2004).

This study also revealed that the reasons for promotion among police officers in Kenya vary, with 12.8% being promoted for efficiency, 26.8% for merit, 10.7% for a combination of discipline, education, and experience, and 4.7% for leadership qualities. Notably, 32.2% did not respond, and 12.8% indicated that the question was not applicable to them. This distribution highlights the diverse criteria used for promotions within the Kenyan police force.

Promotions based on merit and efficiency are indicative of a performance-oriented culture within the police force. Promotions awarded for merit (26.8%) suggest that officers who demonstrate exceptional skills, knowledge, and contributions to their duties are recognized and rewarded. This approach is aligned with the principles of meritocracy, which promotes fairness and motivates officers to excel in their roles (Bayley, 1998). Efficiency-based promotions (12.8%) further reinforce the importance of effective performance, ensuring that officers who can execute their duties proficiently are advanced. This can lead to a more competent and reliable police force, capable of maintaining law and order effectively.

The consideration of discipline, education, and experience (10.7%) as criteria for promotion highlights the value placed on a well-rounded and professionally developed officer. This multifaceted approach ensures that promotions are not only based on performance metrics but also on the personal and professional growth of the officers. Education and experience contribute to the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, while discipline ensures that officers adhere to ethical standards and regulations (Reiner, 2010). Promotions based on leadership qualities (4.7%) emphasize the importance of having capable leaders who can guide and mentor their subordinates, fostering a positive and productive work environment.

The high percentage of non-responses (32.2%) and those indicating the question as not applicable (12.8%) suggests that a significant portion of officers may be either uncertain about the criteria for promotions or feel disconnected from the promotion process. This could indicate issues related to transparency and communication within the force. Ensuring that all officers understand the criteria and process for promotions can enhance trust and morale, making the promotion system more inclusive and equitable (Marenin, 2004).

On the other hand those who have not be promoted , 4.0% attributed their lack of promotion to "God's plan" or a sense of powerlessness, 2.0% cited the absence of promotion boards, 6.7% did not understand the reasons, 3.4% felt they had less experience, 8.7% mentioned not having a senior person, 2.7% had differences with their commanders, and another 2.7% pointed to the limited number of available slots.

The diverse reasons for not being promoted highlight the complex and multifaceted nature of career advancement within the Kenyan police force. The attribution of non-promotion to "God's plan" or powerlessness (4.0%) reflects a cultural and possibly religious belief in fate or divine will, which can impact individual attitudes towards professional growth and agency. This mindset can affect motivation and the pursuit of career development opportunities, potentially leading to a passive acceptance of one's professional status.

The lack of promotion boards (2.0%) and the limited number of slots (2.7%) indicate structural and systemic issues within the police force's promotion processes. The absence of regular promotion boards suggests a possible bureaucratic delay or inefficiency, which can hinder career progression and demoralize officers. Similarly, the limited slots for promotion highlight the competitive nature of advancement within the force, which may lead to frustration among qualified officers who feel their efforts and qualifications are overlooked due to scarcity of opportunities (Reiner, 2010).

The perception of insufficient experience (3.4%) and reliance on senior persons (8.7%) as barriers to promotion reflect traditional hierarchies and the importance placed on tenure over performance. This can create a rigid structure where younger or less experienced officers feel they have limited chances for advancement, regardless of their abilities or contributions. Additionally, interpersonal conflicts with commanders (2.7%) underscore the impact of workplace relationships and power dynamics on career progression, suggesting that personal biases and favoritism can play a role in the promotion process.

D. Knowledge about Police Reforms.

➤ *Awareness of Police Reforms*

This study found high level of awareness of police reforms among Kenyan police officers, with 88.6% of respondents acknowledging their awareness, 8.7% stating they are unaware, and 2.7% not responding. This high level of awareness reflects the substantial efforts made to disseminate information about reforms within the police force.

Ideally, the widespread awareness of police reforms is crucial for their successful implementation. Awareness signifies that the officers are informed about the changes, which can influence their attitudes and behaviors positively towards the reforms. High awareness levels, as indicated by the 88.6%, suggest that the communication channels within the police force are effective in reaching a large portion of the officers. This is essential for fostering a sense of inclusion and participation among the officers in the reform process. When officers are aware of the reforms, they are more likely to understand the rationale behind the changes and how these reforms can impact their work environment and professional development. This can lead to a greater acceptance and cooperation in the reform process, which is essential for meaningful and sustainable changes (Skogan, 2008).

However, the 8.7% of officers who are unaware of the reforms represent a critical gap. This lack of awareness could stem from various factors such as ineffective communication strategies, resistance to change, or a disconnect between the leadership and the lower ranks. It is important for reform initiatives to address these gaps to ensure that no segment of the police force is left behind. Continuous and targeted communication efforts are necessary to reach these officers, addressing their concerns and providing them with the necessary information. Furthermore, the 2.7% non-response rate might indicate indifference or apprehension about expressing opinions on the reforms, which also needs to be addressed to foster a culture of openness and trust within the police force (Bayley, 2008).

Despite majority of the respondents were aware of police reforms, they had varied understanding of police reforms. Out of the 149 respondents, 7.4% associate reforms with housing improvements, 17.4% with matching police units, and another 17.4% with the improvement of work equipment. Other responses include upholding human rights (6.0%), the establishment of oversight bodies like IPOA and internal affairs units (2.0%), change in rotations (6.7%), digitization (2.0%), kitting and police force adjustments (2.0%), salary review and uniform policies (8.7%), reforms in general (6.7%), improved interpersonal relationships (5.4%), and gender equality (2.7%). Additionally, 10.7% did not respond, and 4.7% considered the question not applicable.

These varied interpretations of police reforms highlight the diverse concerns and priorities within the police force. The emphasis on housing and work equipment improvements (24.8% combined) reflects the immediate, practical needs of officers that directly impact their daily lives and job performance. Improved housing can enhance the living conditions of officers, leading to better morale and productivity (Lockwood, 2020). Similarly, better work equipment can improve efficiency and safety, addressing a fundamental aspect of their operational environment.

The responses pointing to human rights, oversight bodies, and gender equality (10.7% combined) indicate a recognition of the broader ethical and institutional aspects of police reforms. This shows an awareness among some officers of the importance of accountability, transparency, and equity within the force. Such awareness is crucial for the legitimacy and trust of the police in the eyes of the public. Reforms aimed at upholding human rights and establishing oversight mechanisms can help in curbing misconduct and fostering a culture of integrity and respect for the law (Bayley, 2008).

The diversity in responses also suggests that police reforms are multifaceted and that officers have different understandings based on their roles, experiences, and personal concerns. This underscores the need for comprehensive and inclusive communication strategies to ensure that all aspects of the reforms are understood and embraced by the officers. Effective reform implementation requires addressing both the material needs and the institutional culture of the police force. Therefore, ongoing education and dialogue about the objectives and benefits of reforms are essential for achieving meaningful and lasting change (Skogan, 2008).

➤ *Impact of Police Reforms.*

The study findings reflect a range of perceptions among Kenyan police officers regarding the impact of police reforms. A significant proportion, 47.7%, believe that reforms have improved their working environment. This indicates that nearly half of the respondents feel that the reforms have had a tangible positive effect on their daily operations and overall job satisfaction. Conversely, 6.7% view the reforms negatively, while 5.4% recognize positive impacts. Other responses include unchanged conditions (4.0%), misunderstanding of the reforms (2.0%), changed membership (5.4%), redeployment issues (1.3%), and confusion and rivalry (2.7%). A notable 16.1% did not respond, suggesting either ambivalence or uncertainty about the impact of reforms.

These findings illustrate the complex and multifaceted nature of police reforms. The improvement of the working environment cited by 47.7% of officers suggests that reforms have addressed some of the structural and operational challenges within the force. Enhanced working conditions can lead to better morale, increased efficiency, and greater job satisfaction, which are critical for maintaining a motivated and effective police force (Skogan, 2008). However, the presence of negative perceptions (6.7%) and confusion (2.7%) highlights the challenges in implementing reforms uniformly and effectively. These negative views may stem from disruptions caused by the reforms or unmet expectations among the officers.

The mixed responses also underscore the importance of clear communication and inclusive participation in the reform process. Misunderstandings and confusion about the reforms, as reported by some officers, can undermine the intended positive outcomes. Ensuring that all officers understand the goals, processes, and benefits of the reforms is essential for their successful implementation. Moreover, the perception of unchanged conditions by 4.0% of respondents indicates that reforms need to be continuously evaluated and adjusted to address any gaps or shortcomings. Engaging officers in the reform process and addressing their concerns can foster a sense of ownership and commitment to the changes being implemented (Bayley, 2008).

Involvement in Police Reforms

The study findings indicate that a substantial portion of Kenyan police officers feel excluded from the reform process, with 52.3% stating they were not involved, while 43.6% reported being involved, and 4.0% did not respond. This suggests that more than half of the officers feel disconnected from the changes being implemented within their institution, potentially leading to a lack of ownership and commitment to the reforms.

involvement of police officers in reform processes is crucial for the successful implementation and sustainability of changes. Inclusion fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment among officers, which can enhance their commitment to and compliance with new policies and procedures (Skogan, 2008). When officers are involved, they are more likely to understand the rationale behind reforms and be motivated to support and implement them effectively. This involvement can also provide valuable insights from frontline officers that can shape more practical and effective reform measures (Bayley, 2008).

The fact that a majority of officers reported not being involved points to potential issues in the reform process. This lack of involvement could lead to resistance or apathy towards reforms, as officers may perceive them as top-down mandates that do not consider their perspectives or the realities of their work environment (Reiner, 2010). Effective reform requires not only top-level directives but also grassroots involvement to ensure that changes are both practical and accepted by those who are expected to implement them. Policymakers and police leadership should therefore prioritize mechanisms for meaningful participation and feedback from officers at all levels to bridge this gap and foster a more inclusive and supportive environment for reform (Maguire, 2014).

The study findings also reveal that the involvement of Kenyan police officers in various aspects of police reforms is limited and varied. Specifically, 12.8% of officers were involved in proposing areas of improvement, 14.8% participated in decision-making processes, 3.4% were engaged in sensitization activities, 4.0% responded to questionnaires by the National Police Service, and 3.4% were involved in policy implementation. These figures suggest that while there is some level of engagement, it is not widespread, and the majority of officers are not significantly involved in the reform processes.

The distribution of involvement among police officers highlights several important issues. The relatively low percentages across different areas of involvement indicate that reforms are still largely top-down rather than participatory. Proposing areas of improvement (12.8%) and decision-making (14.8%) are critical for fostering a sense of ownership and ensuring that the reforms are practical and address the real needs and challenges faced by officers on the ground (Skogan, 2008). When officers are actively engaged in these processes, they are more likely to support and effectively implement changes, leading to more sustainable reforms.

The low engagement in sensitization (3.4%) and policy implementation (3.4%) suggests that there is a significant gap in communication and practical application of reforms. Sensitization is crucial for ensuring that all officers understand the purpose and benefits of reforms, which can help mitigate resistance and enhance cooperation (Bayley, 2008). Furthermore, involvement in policy implementation ensures that reforms are not only well-conceived but also effectively put into practice. The minimal involvement in responding to questionnaires (4.0%) also points to a lack of comprehensive feedback mechanisms that could provide valuable insights from officers' experiences and perspectives.

Overall, the findings underscore the need for a more inclusive and participatory approach to police reforms in Kenya. Engaging a broader base of officers in various stages of the reform process can enhance the legitimacy and effectiveness of reforms. Policymakers and police leadership should prioritize creating avenues for meaningful participation, feedback, and communication to ensure that reforms are both practical and widely accepted (Maguire, 2014; Reiner, 2010).

This study also found that a significant portion, 20.5%, were unaware of the reasons for their non-involvement in police reforms, while 19.4% attributed their lack of involvement to their low rank. This data highlights critical issues related to communication, transparency, and hierarchical barriers within the police force.

The fact that 20.5% of officers do not know why they are not involved in reforms suggests a significant gap in communication and information dissemination within the police force. Effective organizational change, especially in a structured institution like the police, requires clear communication of the objectives, processes, and roles of every member. When officers are not informed about the reasons behind their exclusion, it can lead to feelings of alienation and disengagement, which can undermine the effectiveness of the reforms (Skogan, 2008). This situation underscores the need for police leadership to enhance transparency and ensure that all officers are aware of the ongoing changes and their potential roles in these processes.

The fact that 19.4% of officers cited their low rank as the reason for their non-involvement points to the rigid hierarchical structure of the police force. In many police organizations, rank often determines the level of participation in decision-making processes (Reiner, 2010). Lower-ranked officers may feel that their insights and experiences are undervalued, leading to a top-down approach to reforms that may not fully address on-the-ground realities. This hierarchical barrier can stifle innovation and the practical implementation of reforms, as lower-ranked officers are often the ones directly interacting with the community and dealing with day-to-day challenges (Bayley, 2008). Addressing this issue requires creating more inclusive platforms where officers of all ranks can contribute to reform discussions, thereby democratizing the reform process and ensuring it is informed by diverse perspectives.

➤ *Who Institutes Police Reforms*

The findings reveal that 55% of the respondents indicated that the National Police Service Commission (NPSC) is primarily involved in instituting police reforms in Kenya. Meanwhile, 22.8% of the respondents did not provide a response, and 22.1% considered the question not applicable to them. This data reflects the central role of the NPSC in driving reforms and highlights a significant gap in awareness or perception among the officers regarding the entities responsible for reforms.

The prominent role of the NPSC in police reforms aligns with the structural-functionalism theory, which emphasizes the importance of organized bodies in maintaining social order and implementing systematic changes (Parsons, 1951). The NPSC, as a structured and officially mandated body, is designed to oversee and implement reforms that ensure the police force functions efficiently and adheres to modern standards. However, the significant proportion of non-responses and those considering the question inapplicable (45%) suggests a disconnect between the reform initiatives at the top and the understanding or engagement of the lower ranks within the police force. This disconnect can hinder the effective implementation of reforms, as the lack of awareness or involvement can lead to resistance or apathy among the officers who are expected to carry out these changes (Skogan, 2008).

Additionally, the data may reflect a broader issue of communication and inclusivity within the police reform process. The high percentage of non-responses indicates that a substantial number of officers might feel disconnected or uninformed about the reform activities. This situation can be analyzed using the conflict theory, which posits that power and resource disparities within institutions can lead to friction and inefficiencies (Marx, 1867). The perception that reforms are driven solely by a centralized body like the NPSC, without sufficient engagement of the broader police force, can exacerbate feelings of disenfranchisement and disempowerment among lower-ranked officers. For reforms to be successful and sustainable, it is crucial to ensure that all members of the police force are not only aware of but also actively involved in the reform processes. This approach can enhance the sense of ownership and accountability, leading to more effective and lasting changes (Reiner, 2010).

➤ *Information about Police Reforms.*

The study findings indicate that 81.2% of the police officers surveyed reported having information about police reforms, while 14.8% indicated they did not have such information, and 4% did not respond. This majority awareness is a positive indicator of the dissemination of reform-related information within the police force, suggesting that most officers are at least aware of ongoing changes and initiatives.

The study findings also reveal that police officers rely on diverse sources of information regarding police reforms among Kenyan police officers. The most significant source is senior officers, media, and rallies, accounting for 26.2% of the responses. This is followed by the National Police Service Commission at 17.4%, media at 14.1%, and parliamentary proceedings at 11.4%. Training sessions are also a notable source at 10.1%. Other sources include the constitution and police meetings (1.3%) and a combination of these sources. Notably, 18.1% did not respond, and 1.3% found the information not applicable.

The reliance on senior officers, media, and rallies as primary sources of information highlights the role of hierarchical communication and public discourse in shaping officers' understanding of reforms. The fact that senior officers are a major source suggests that top-down communication is a dominant method within the police force. This can be attributed to desire for maintaining a unified message but may also lead to information filtering and potential biases if not balanced with other sources (Tourish & Robson, 2006).

The involvement of the National Police Service Commission as a notable source of information reflects the institutional efforts to formalize and standardize the dissemination of reform-related information. However, the 18.1% of non-responses could indicate gaps in communication strategies, highlighting areas where the dissemination of information might be inadequate. This gap can lead to disparities in knowledge and preparedness among officers, affecting the overall implementation of reforms. Effective communication strategies should therefore aim to reach all members of the organization, ensuring inclusivity and comprehensive understanding.

➤ *General Construction of Police Reforms*

The findings suggest that Kenyan police officers perceive police reforms primarily as a means to improve public perception of the police (39.6%) and enhance work performance (29.5%). A smaller portion views reforms as fostering a sense of responsibility (3.4%), teamwork (2.0%), and police reform itself (4.0%). Notably, 20.1% did not respond, and 1.3% indicated they did not know the purpose of the reforms.

The high percentage of officers seeing reforms as a way to improve public perception indicates an awareness of the critical role that public trust and legitimacy play in policing. This aligns with the concept of institutional legitimacy, where institutions seek to align with societal values and norms to maintain public trust (Tyler, 2006). Improving public perception can lead to increased cooperation and compliance from the public, which is essential for effective policing (Sunshine & Tyler, 2003). The smaller percentages associated with responsibility, teamwork, and the reform process itself reflect varied interpretations of the reform goals. Viewing reforms as fostering a sense of responsibility and teamwork suggests a shift towards more collaborative and accountable policing practices.

The 20.1% non-response rate indicates a significant portion of officers may feel disconnected from the reform process or lack sufficient information. This gap underscores the need for effective communication and involvement strategies to ensure that all officers understand and engage with the reforms. Effective communication and training programs can address these gaps, ensuring that reforms are uniformly understood and implemented across the police force (Robinson, 2011).

➤ *Individual Social Construction of Police Reforms*

The study findings reveal diverse individual social constructions of police reforms among police officers in Kenya. A significant proportion perceive police reforms as aimed at improving service delivery (40.9%), reflecting a focus on enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of police operations. Another prevalent construction is the desire to make work easier (19.5%), indicating that some officers view reforms as an opportunity to streamline procedures and reduce bureaucratic hurdles within the police force. A smaller yet significant portion of officers associate reforms with upholding human rights (7.4%).

Less frequently cited constructions include perceptions of reforms as addressing rampant corruption (3.4%), enhancing motivation (4.7%), and addressing intimidation (1.3%). These perspectives highlight specific challenges within the police force that reforms are expected to mitigate or resolve. The presence of responses such as "don't know" (1.3%) and non-responses (20.1%) suggests potential gaps in understanding or communication within the police force regarding the objectives and expected outcomes of reform initiatives.

E. Attitudes towards Police Reforms

➤ *Police Reforms Make Officers Responsible*

The study findings show that a substantial majority of police officers, totaling 84.6% had favorable attitudes towards police reforms intended to increase responsibility in their duties. This high level of agreement suggests a significant alignment between the goals of the reforms and the perceptions of officers regarding their roles and responsibilities within the police force. Sociologically, this alignment can be interpreted through the lens of institutional legitimacy, where the police force seeks to maintain trust and confidence from the public and within its own ranks by promoting accountability and professionalism (Tyler, 2006).

On the other hand, 8.2 % had unfavorable attitudes and 5.4% indicate no opinion regarding the police reforms. The fact that a small percentage expressed who unfavorable attitudes police reforms as aimed at enhancing responsibility highlights potential areas of concern or skepticism within the police organization

➤ *Vetting/ Screening of Police Officers to Determine Suitability.*

In this study, a significant portion, comprising 67.7% who either strongly agree (26.8%) or agree (40.9%), had favorable attitudes towards the idea of vetting or screening of police officers to determine their suitability in continuing serving in police service. This positive attitude can be interpreted as a reflection of the growing recognition within law enforcement of the importance of maintaining professionalism and integrity. Vetting processes are seen as mechanisms to ensure that officers meet ethical standards, possess the necessary competencies, and are fit for duty, thus enhancing public trust and organizational legitimacy (Tyler, 2006).

Conversely, 21.4% of officers either expressed uncertainty (12.1%), disagreed (8.7%), or strongly disagreed (2.7%) with vetting or screening processes which indicates unfavorable attitudes. This viewpoint could stem from various factors. Some officers as noted during informal discussions perceived vetting as intrusive or distrusted the fairness of the process as they perceived it as not conducted transparently or consistently. Others questioned the effectiveness of vetting in identifying and addressing issues such as corruption or misconduct within the police ranks. Such skepticism underscores the complexity of implementing vetting processes within police organizations, where perceptions of fairness and procedural justice are crucial (Tyler, 2006).

➤ *Police Reforms and Community Policing*

This study found out that majority of police officers hold positive attitudes towards police reforms in enhancing community policing, with 81.9% either strongly agreeing (34.2%) or agreeing (47.7%) with these initiatives. This strong endorsement can be interpreted as a recognition among officers of the benefits and effectiveness of community policing in improving public safety and enhancing police-community relations (Skogan & Hartnett, 1997). Community policing emphasizes collaboration between police and local communities, focusing on proactive problem-solving and building trust through increased officer visibility and engagement (Trojanowicz & Bucqueroux, 1990).

The minority who expressed uncertainty (6.7%), disagreement (4.0%), or did not respond (7.4%) indicate varying perceptions or reservations about the feasibility or effectiveness of police reforms in enhancing community policing. Some officers as noted in informal discussions questioned the effectiveness of police reforms in enhancing community policing in a context of limited resources to facilitate police operations.

➤ *Police Reforms and Treating the Public Fair*

The study findings reveal that a substantial majority of police officers hold positive attitudes towards police reforms as enhancing fair treatment of the public. Specifically, 78.5% of officers either strongly agree (39.6%) or agree (38.9%) that these reforms are necessary. This strong endorsement reflects a recognition of the importance of procedural justice within policing practices. Procedural justice theory posits that when police officers treat people with fairness, respect, and transparency, it enhances the legitimacy of the police in the eyes of the public (Tyler, 2006).

The 8.1% of officers who are uncertain ("don't know") and the 4.7% who disagree with the importance of these reforms might reflect a range of factors, including a lack of understanding of procedural justice principles, skepticism about the feasibility of implementing these reforms, or resistance to change due to ingrained practices and cultural norms within the police force. Addressing these concerns through targeted training and continuous dialogue can help bridge these gaps and foster a more uniform commitment to fair treatment principles.

The 8.7% of officers who did not respond may indicate either a disengagement from the reform discourse or uncertainty about the implications of these changes. Ensuring that all officers are well-informed and actively engaged in discussions about the importance and benefits of procedural justice is crucial for the successful implementation of these reforms.

➤ *Police Reforms and Police Officers' Welfare*

The study findings reveal that a majority of police officers in Kenya hold positive attitudes towards police reforms aimed at improving their welfare, with 59.7% of respondents either strongly agreeing (26.2%) or agreeing (33.6%) with this view. However, there is also a notable proportion of officers who either disagree (15.4%) or strongly disagree (8.7%) with this statement, while 8.1% are unsure ("don't know") and another 8.1% did not respond

The favorable attitudes towards welfare improvements can be understood through the concept of institutional trust. When police officers perceive that reforms are genuinely aimed at enhancing their welfare—such as better working conditions, fair salaries, and adequate support systems—it can boost their morale and commitment to their duties. High morale among officers is crucial for effective policing, as it reduces stress, increases job satisfaction, and promotes a sense of loyalty and professionalism within the force (Maguire & King, 2004).

According to social exchange theory, individuals are more likely to perform well and remain committed to their roles when they feel valued and supported by their organization. Police reforms that focus on welfare improvements can be seen as a form of social exchange, where the institution provides better conditions and, in return, expects enhanced performance and accountability from officers (Blau, 1964). This reciprocal relationship can lead to a more motivated and efficient police force.

The significant minority of officers who disagree or strongly disagree with the statement about welfare improvements may reflect resistance to change. As found out from informal discussions resistance to police reform stem from several factors including fear of the unknown, skepticism about the sincerity of reform efforts, or past experiences where promised reforms did not materialize. Additionally, ingrained cultural norms and practices within the police force can make some officers wary of new initiatives (Skogan, 2008).

The 8.1% who are unsure and the same percentage who did not respond suggest gaps in communication and information dissemination regarding the reforms. Effective communication strategies are essential to ensure that all officers understand the objectives and benefits of the reforms. Transparent and continuous dialogue between leadership and officers can help address uncertainties and build a collective commitment to the reforms.

➤ *Police Reforms and Service Delivery*

The study findings indicate that a majority of police officers have a positive attitude towards police reforms aimed at improving service delivery. Specifically, 67.8% of the respondents either strongly agree (26.2%) or agree (41.6%) that the reforms will enhance service delivery. However, there is also a notable portion of officers who are either unsure ("don't know" at 5.4%), disagree (7.4%), or strongly disagree (7.4%) with this statement. Additionally, 10.1% of respondents did not respond.

The high percentage of officers agreeing that reforms will improve service delivery reflects a perception of increased legitimacy and effectiveness of the police force. When officers believe that reforms are designed to enhance their ability to perform their duties, it can lead to greater motivation and commitment. This perception aligns with the theory of procedural justice, which posits that fair and transparent processes lead to higher compliance and cooperation (Tyler, 2006). Officers who see reforms as fair and aimed at improving their work conditions are more likely to support and engage with these changes.

The presence of officers who disagree or strongly disagree with the reforms highlights the potential resistance to change within the organization. This resistance can stem from several factors, including entrenched organizational cultures, fear of losing power or status, and skepticism about the effectiveness of the reforms (Burke, 2013). In policing, where traditions and routines are deeply ingrained, introducing new ways of working can be met with resistance. The 5.4% of officers who are unsure about the impact of the reforms and the 10.1% who did not respond indicate gaps in communication and information dissemination within the police force.

➤ *Police Reforms and Motivation*

The findings indicate that a substantial portion of police officers in Kenya have positive attitudes towards the reforms in terms of enhancing motivation. Specifically, 54.4% either strongly agree (20.8%) or agree (33.6%) that the reforms will enhance motivation. However, a significant minority are either unsure ("don't know" at 10.7%), disagree (18.1%), or strongly disagree (6.7%) with this statement. Additionally, 10.1% of respondents did not respond.

Sociologically reforms that aim to improve working conditions, provide better equipment, and increase professional development opportunities can enhance intrinsic motivation. Officers may feel a greater sense of job satisfaction and professional pride when they perceive their work environment as supportive and their skills as valued (Deci & Ryan, 2000). This aligns with self-determination theory, which posits that autonomy, competence, and relatedness are key drivers

The agreement by 54.4% of officers suggests a readiness for change within the police force. This readiness is crucial for successful implementation of reforms. According to Lewin's change management model, this stage is akin to the 'unfreezing' phase, where the organization prepares for change by recognizing the need for it (Lewin, 1947). The 24.8% who disagree or strongly disagree, coupled with the 10.7% who are unsure, highlight the presence of resistance to change. The 10.7% of officers who do not know if reforms will enhance motivation indicate gaps in communication and information dissemination.

➤ *Police Reforms and Fairness in Police Service*

The findings from the study reveal a diverse range of attitudes among Kenyan police officers regarding the impact of police reforms on enhancing fairness within the police service. A notable majority of officers, 57.7%, either strongly agree or agree that the reforms enhance fairness, indicating a significant alignment with the goals of the reforms.

However, the data also uncovers resistance and uncertainty among a sizable minority of officers. Specifically, 22.2% of officers either disagree or strongly disagree with the notion that reforms enhance fairness, while 8.7% are unsure. This resistance could stem from a perception of unequal distribution of the benefits of reforms, such as promotions or access to resources, which raises concerns about distributive justice. Additionally, the presence of a significant portion of officers who are either uncertain or non-responsive

points to gaps in communication and engagement within the reform process. These gaps suggest that more inclusive and transparent approaches are needed to ensure that all officers understand and support the changes.

➤ *Police Reforms and Corruption*

The findings reveal a predominantly negative attitude among Kenyan police officers towards the impact of police reforms on reducing corruption within the force. Only 15.5% of officers either strongly agree or agree that the reforms have a positive effect on reducing corruption, indicating a significant skepticism regarding the efficacy of these measures. This skepticism is further underscored by the fact that a substantial majority, 55.7%, either disagree or strongly disagree with the notion that reforms are effectively tackling corruption. Additionally, 14.1% of officers are uncertain, and 14.8% did not respond, suggesting a notable degree of ambivalence or disengagement on this issue.

This resistance and skepticism can be explained through the lens of organizational culture and the entrenched nature of corruption within institutions. Corruption often becomes a deeply ingrained part of an organization's culture, with established norms and practices that are resistant to change. The high level of disagreement among officers may reflect a perception that the reforms are either superficial or inadequately implemented, failing to address the root causes of corruption. This perception can be compounded by a lack of trust in the reform process, particularly if officers feel that the measures are externally imposed or lack genuine commitment from leadership.

Furthermore, the significant portion of officers who are unsure or did not respond suggests a need for more transparent and inclusive communication regarding the anti-corruption aspects of the reforms. Effective anti-corruption initiatives require not only robust policies but also a cultural shift within the organization, where ethical behavior is promoted and corruption is actively discouraged. This can be achieved through comprehensive training, clear and consistent enforcement of anti-corruption measures, and a demonstrable commitment from senior leadership. Addressing these issues is crucial for fostering a culture of integrity within the police force, which is essential for the legitimacy and effectiveness of policing in Kenya.

F. *Police Reforms and Practices*

➤ *Comfortable with Police Reforms*

The study findings indicate that a significant majority of police officers in Kenya, comprising 67%, are comfortable with the ongoing police reforms, while 28% are not comfortable, and 5% did not respond. This high level of comfort among a majority of officers suggests that many within the force view the reforms positively, perceiving them as beneficial or necessary for their work environment and professional development. However, the fact that over a quarter of the officers are uncomfortable with the reforms indicates that there are still considerable reservations and potential resistance within the force.

The fact that majority of the police officers are comfortable with police reforms is seen as indicative of successful alignment between the reform goals and the needs or expectations of the officers. Reforms that improve working conditions, enhance accountability, and provide clear benefits to officers are likely to be more readily accepted. This acceptance aligns with theories of organizational change, which suggest that employees are more likely to support changes when they perceive them as addressing their interests or improving their professional environment.

On the other hand, the discomfort expressed by 28% of the officers highlights the challenges associated with implementing reforms in a complex and historically rigid institution like the police force. This discomfort can be attributed to various factors, such as fear of the unknown, potential disruptions to established practices, and perceived threats to job security or autonomy. Additionally, resistance to change is often rooted in the existing organizational culture, which may be deeply resistant to new ways of operating, particularly if the reforms are seen as externally imposed without sufficient consultation or involvement of the rank-and-file officers.

The 5% non-response rate may reflect a segment of the force that is either disengaged or uncertain about the reforms, indicating a need for better communication and inclusion in the reform process. For reforms to be genuinely effective, it is crucial to address the concerns of all stakeholders, provide adequate support and training, and foster an inclusive environment where all officers feel heard and involved in the transformation process. This approach can help bridge the gap between those who are comfortable with the changes and those who are not, ultimately leading to a more cohesive and effective police force.

Among the police officers who were comfortable with police reforms, a substantial proportion of officers, 36.8%, feel that the reforms improve community policing. Another 16.8% believe that the reforms enhance public attitudes toward the police, while 7.4% cite motivation and implementation as reasons for their comfort. Additionally, 6% of officers appreciate the reforms for fostering professionalism within the force.

The perception that police reforms improve community policing aligns with the idea that reforms are seen as enhancing the relationship between the police and the community. This perspective supports the community-oriented policing model, which emphasizes collaboration between the police and the community to address issues of public safety and crime prevention. When

officers perceive that reforms are facilitating better community engagement, it can lead to increased job satisfaction and a sense of accomplishment, as they see tangible improvements in their work environment and community relations.

Police reforms were also seen as improving public attitudes toward the police thus increasing police legitimacy and trust in the eyes of the public. In this regard, during informal discussions some police officers felt that reforms were positively shaping public perceptions making them experience a heightened sense of pride and validation in their roles. In addition, the recognition of reforms contributing to motivation, implementation, and professionalism highlights the internal benefits perceived by officers.

As noted in this study among the 28% of the police officers who were uncomfortable with police reforms, 18% believe that the reforms have caused more harm than good, 7.4% argue that the reforms have only been partially implemented, thus making it difficult to assess their impact fully, and 2.6% feel that the reforms have created uncertainty.

The belief held by 18% of officers that reforms have caused more harm than good suggests a possible disruption of established norms and practices within the police force. According to the theory of organizational change, any significant alteration in an institution's operations can lead to resistance, especially if the changes are perceived as threatening existing power structures or job security (Burke, 2013). This resistance is often rooted in a fear of the unknown and a reluctance to abandon familiar routines, which can be perceived as more reliable and stable compared to new, untested reforms.

The 7.4% of officers who argue that reforms have only been partly implemented and thus difficult to quantify may highlight issues related to the implementation process itself. Incomplete or inconsistent implementation can lead to confusion and frustration among officers, undermining their confidence in the reform efforts. This can arise when reforms are seen as haphazard or poorly executed thus fail to gain the legitimacy needed to be effective (Tyler, 2006). Lastly, the 2.6% of officers who feel that reforms have created uncertainty are likely experiencing the destabilizing effects of organizational change. Uncertainty in the workplace can lead to stress and anxiety, which can negatively impact job performance and morale.

➤ *Police Reforms and Performance*

The study findings indicate varied perceptions among police officers regarding the impact of police reforms on their performance. A significant portion of officers, 43%, reported that the reforms have improved their observance of human rights. This suggests that the reforms have successfully instilled a greater awareness and respect for human rights within the force, aligning policing practices with broader societal expectations of ethical behavior and justice. Such an improvement can be seen as a positive outcome of the reforms, potentially leading to enhanced public trust and legitimacy of the police force.

Another 14.8% of officers indicated that the reforms have positively impacted their motivation. This boost in motivation can be attributed to various factors, including improved working conditions, better training, and professional development opportunities introduced by the reforms. When officers feel valued and supported by their organization, their job satisfaction and commitment to their duties tend to increase.

Conversely, a smaller portion of officers reported negative impacts: 3.4% said the reforms have created fear, and 1.3% mentioned changes in social welfare. The creation of fear may stem from uncertainty and apprehension about the changes brought by the reforms, potentially linked to increased scrutiny and accountability measures. This fear could be indicative of resistance to change, a common phenomenon in organizational transformations where employees feel threatened by new expectations and standards (Burke, 2013).

The remaining responses, with 6.7% stating that the reforms have not had much impact and 22.8% not responding, suggest varying degrees of disengagement or skepticism about the effectiveness of the reforms. This ambivalence can be attributed to inadequate communication or perceived inconsistencies in the implementation of the reforms.

➤ *Individual Actions Towards Police Reforms*

In this study police reforms elicited a range of reactions among individual officers, reflecting diverse motivations and attitudes. Approximately 24.5% of officers support and adapt to the reforms, viewing them as opportunities for professional growth and enhanced service delivery. These officers align their personal values with institutional goals, actively engaging with new training programs and adhering to updated protocols to build community trust and improve job satisfaction. Conversely, 14.4% of officers exhibit resistance and skepticism, driven by fears of losing control and doubts about the reforms' effectiveness. This skepticism often stems from past experiences where similar initiatives failed to produce tangible improvements, leading to a lack of trust in new measures.

A significant 38.1% of officers adapt to reforms for personal gain, exploiting new procedures and community initiatives to enhance their influence and secure resources, thus undermining the reforms' intended outcomes. Another 20.1% comply out of fear of disciplinary actions or exposure of past misconduct, resulting in superficial adherence without meaningful behavioral change. Lastly, 2.9% of officers experience burnout and resignation, overwhelmed by the demands of implementing reforms and choosing to leave the force for alternative careers.

➤ *Overall Perception about Police Reforms*

The study findings reveal that a substantial majority of police officers in Kenya (82.6%) perceive police reforms positively, indicating a broad acceptance or support for these initiatives. This high level of approval suggests that many officers recognize the potential benefits of reforms, such as improved transparency, accountability, and professional development. The positive perception stemmed from experiences where reforms have led to better training, clearer guidelines, and enhanced community relations, contributing to a more effective and respected police force.

However, 11.4% of officers express a negative perception of the reforms, indicating resistance or dissatisfaction. This group were influenced by concerns about the impact of reforms on their autonomy, job security, or traditional practices within the force. The 6% of officers did not respond to this question.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Introduction

This chapter summarizes the research findings and draws conclusion. In addition, it gives recommendations and suggestions for future study.

B. Summary of major findings.

➤ Knowledge about Police Reforms

The study on police reforms in Kenya reveals a high level of awareness among officers, with 88.6% acknowledging their awareness of reforms, reflecting effective communication within the police force. However, the 8.7% who are unaware and the 2.7% non-respondents highlight gaps that need addressing. Officers associate reforms with various improvements, such as housing, work equipment, and human rights, indicating diverse concerns and priorities within the force. This varied understanding underscores the importance of comprehensive communication to ensure all officers grasp the reforms' full scope.

Regarding the impact of reforms, 47.7% of officers report improvements in their working environment, demonstrating positive structural and operational changes. However, 6.7% view the reforms negatively, and some officers report confusion or unchanged conditions, pointing to implementation challenges. Clear communication and continuous evaluation of reforms are essential to address these issues and ensure their effectiveness.

Involvement in the reform process is a significant concern, with 52.3% of officers feeling excluded, which can lead to resistance or apathy. Only 43.6% reported being involved in any reform activities, highlighting a need for more inclusive participation. Lower-ranked officers often feel their insights are undervalued, suggesting hierarchical barriers hinder effective reform implementation. Policymakers must prioritize inclusive participation to foster ownership and commitment to reforms.

The study also shows that 81.2% of officers have information about reforms, primarily sourced from senior officers, media, and rallies. This reliance on hierarchical communication and public discourse indicates the need for diversified and inclusive information channels to ensure comprehensive understanding across all ranks. Training sessions also play a crucial role in disseminating reform-related information.

Finally, officers' perceptions of police reforms are primarily centered on improving public perception (39.6%) and enhancing work performance (29.5%). Additionally, many officers view reforms as a means to improve service delivery and streamline procedures. However, significant non-responses and varied individual interpretations suggest gaps in understanding and communication. Addressing these gaps through effective communication and training is vital for the successful implementation and acceptance of reforms.

➤ Attitudes towards Police Reforms

The study found out that police had varied attitudes towards police reforms. The majority of officers demonstrate strong support for reforms aimed at increasing responsibility within their duties (84.6%) and enhancing community policing efforts (81.9%). These findings suggest a widespread recognition among officers of the benefits of accountability and community engagement in improving public safety and police-community relations.

Additionally, a significant portion of officers (78.5%) express positive attitudes towards reforms aimed at promoting fair treatment of the public. This reflects a consensus among many officers regarding the importance of procedural justice in enhancing the legitimacy of policing practices.

However, the study also reveals notable areas of skepticism and uncertainty. For instance, there is limited optimism among officers regarding the effectiveness of reforms in reducing corruption within the police force, with only 15.5% expressing positive views in this regard. This skepticism underscores persistent concerns about the entrenched nature of corruption and the efficacy of current reform measures in addressing systemic issues.

Mixed attitudes were evident towards other reform aspects as well. While a substantial majority (67.7%) support vetting processes to determine officers' suitability, there is variability in views concerning reforms aimed at enhancing service delivery (67.8%) and officer motivation (54.4%). These variations highlight differing perceptions among officers regarding the potential impacts of reforms on their working conditions and professional satisfaction.

Overall, while there is considerable support for reforms aimed at enhancing accountability, community engagement, and fair treatment practices, challenges remain in addressing skepticism towards corruption reduction efforts and ensuring consistent support across all reform areas. Efforts to improve communication, transparency in reform implementation, and ongoing dialogue with officers are crucial to fostering broader acceptance and commitment to these reform initiatives

➤ *Practices Towards Police Reforms.*

A majority of officers (67%) expressed support for ongoing reforms, seeing them as advantageous for enhancing work environments and professional growth. This acceptance underscores the perceived alignment between reform objectives and officers' interests, supporting theories that employees are more likely to endorse changes that directly benefit them. However, a significant minority (28%) express discomfort with reforms, citing concerns such as potential negative impacts, incomplete implementation, or uncertainties about the reform process. These reservations highlight enduring challenges within the police force, including resistance to change and anxieties about job stability amid institutional transformations.

Regarding performance impacts, many officers (43%) note improvements in human rights adherence, signaling a positive shift toward ethical policing practices that bolster public confidence. Conversely, a small fraction (3.4%) express apprehensions related to reforms, particularly regarding heightened scrutiny and accountability measures. Additionally, a notable portion of officers (29.5%) either report minimal effects or withhold responses, indicating varying levels of engagement and skepticism toward the efficacy of reforms. This diversity of perspectives underscores the necessity for clearer communication and consistent implementation to ensure widespread understanding and acceptance of reforms across the force.

Individual responses to reforms further reveal diverse motivations among officers: some endorse reforms for professional advancement and service enhancement (24.5%), while others exhibit resistance (14.4%), adapt for personal gain (38.1%), comply reluctantly (20.1%), or experience burnout (2.9%). These varied reactions underscore the intricate dynamics influencing reform outcomes within the police force, including organizational culture, perceptions of fairness, and alignment with personal and institutional objectives.

Last but not least, while a significant majority of officers (82.6%) view reforms positively, recognizing benefits such as improved transparency and professional development, addressing challenges like resistance, inconsistent implementation, and fostering broader engagement remains pivotal for sustaining reform success in Kenya.

In conclusion, this this mixed perception among police officers towards police reforms. While there is generally high awareness, significant gaps exist in understanding and participation. Reforms are seen positively for improving aspects like working conditions and human rights, but challenges such as confusion over implementation and resistance due to job stability concerns persist. Many officers feel excluded from the reform process, relying heavily on hierarchical communication channels. Attitudes vary, with strong support for accountability and community policing, yet skepticism remains about the effectiveness of corruption reduction efforts. Addressing these issues requires improved communication strategies, inclusive participation, and efforts to align reform goals with officers' expectations to ensure successful implementation across the Kenyan police force.

C. Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study on police reforms in Kenya, several recommendations can be made to address the identified challenges and enhance the effectiveness of reforms:

- **Develop Comprehensive Communication Strategies:** It is crucial to develop communication strategies that transcend traditional hierarchical channels within the police force. Utilizing diverse methods such as workshops, seminars, and digital platforms ensures that all officers, regardless of rank, receive timely and accurate information about ongoing reforms. This approach not only enhances transparency but also fosters a shared understanding of reform goals and objectives across the entire organization.
- **Foster Inclusive Participation:** To promote a culture of inclusivity, officers from all ranks should be actively involved in the reform process. Forming reform committees that represent diverse roles and responsibilities within the police force can ensure that every voice is heard and valued. By encouraging participation at all levels, from frontline officers to senior management, reform initiatives can benefit from a broad spectrum of perspectives and insights, leading to more informed decision-making and greater buy-in from the entire workforce.
- **Clearly Articulate Reform Goals and Benefits:** Clear and transparent communication of reform goals, benefits, and expected outcomes is essential to gaining support and reducing skepticism among officers. Emphasizing how reforms will positively impact their work environment, professional development, and public perception helps officers understand the relevance and importance of changes. This clarity builds confidence in the reform process and aligns individual expectations with organizational objectives, fostering a supportive environment for implementation.
- **Address Implementation Challenges:** Regular evaluations and feedback sessions are critical to addressing implementation challenges effectively. By identifying and promptly resolving issues such as procedural confusion or perceived negative impacts, police leadership can maintain momentum and morale among officers. This proactive approach ensures that reform efforts remain on track and responsive to evolving operational needs, enhancing the likelihood of successful outcomes.
- **Proactively Address Resistance:** Addressing resistance to reforms requires proactive engagement with officers to understand their concerns and motivations. Tailoring communication and training efforts to address specific barriers and misconceptions helps build trust and commitment among officers. By involving them in the change process and demonstrating the benefits of reforms in practical terms, leaders can mitigate resistance and promote a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation within the police force.

- **Provide Comprehensive Training Programs:** Effective reform implementation hinges on equipping officers with the necessary skills and knowledge. Comprehensive training programs should not only educate officers about the rationale behind reforms but also provide practical guidance on how to implement new policies and procedures effectively. This investment in professional development ensures that officers are well-prepared to adapt to changing operational environments and contribute positively to reform objectives.
- **Establish Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms:** Robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are essential for tracking the progress and impact of reforms over time. Using data-driven insights from these mechanisms enables leaders to refine strategies, address emerging challenges, and celebrate successes within the police force. Continuous evaluation ensures that reforms remain aligned with organizational goals and responsive to the evolving needs of officers and the community they serve.
- **Uphold Accountability and Transparency:** Upholding principles of accountability and transparency throughout the reform process is fundamental to building trust and credibility. Implementing clear mechanisms to hold all stakeholders accountable, including senior officers and policymakers, ensures that commitments to reform are honored and outcomes are achieved. This commitment to transparency fosters a culture of integrity and responsibility within the police force, enhancing public trust and confidence in policing practices.

D. Recommendation for Further Research

This study proposes qualitative research focusing on the lived experiences of police officers with police reforms. This approach will augment the current study on perceptions of police reforms by officers in Kenya. By exploring officers' personal narratives and firsthand accounts, qualitative research can provide deeper insights into their attitudes, motivations, and concerns regarding the reforms. It will also allow for a further understanding of the complexities of reform implementation and its impact on officers' daily work and professional development.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: LETTER TO THE RESPONDENTS

To respondent

RE: LETTER OF INTRODUCTION AND REQUEST TO CONDUCT RESEARCH.

I am a student at Moi University. I am conducting research in partial requirement for the award of a master of arts in governance and ethics degree of Moi University on “Perception of police reforms by members of national police service: A case study of Kisumu County. You have been selected in this target area to support the research since your input is important in several ways. The study aims at adding knowledge to existing research data.

The research will involve interviewing and administering questionnaires to key personnel who are involved in strategic practices and in this corporate area. You are therefore kindly requested to answer all the questions as per the instructions given. Any information provided will make this study more meaningful and all information gathered will purely go into benefiting this purpose and thus will be confidentially treated. Your cooperation in participating in this study will be highly appreciated.

Thank you in advance

Yours faithfully,

Sign..... Date.....

GETEMBE EVANS MOMANYI

Reg.No: SASS/PGS/01/2014

APPENDIX 2: RESEARCH PERMIT

REPUBLIC OF KENYA

**NATIONAL COMMISSION FOR
SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY & INNOVATION**

Ref No: 756393 Date of Issue: 13/January/2023

RESEARCH LICENSE

This is to Certify that Mr. EVANS MWANGI GETEMBA of Moi University, has been licensed to conduct research in Kisumu on the topic: PERCEPTIONS OF POLICE REFORMS BY MEMBERS OF NATIONAL POLICE SERVICE: A CASE STUDY OF KISUMU COUNTY for the period ending : 13/January/2023.

License No: NACOSTIP/22/15207

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APPENDIX 3: QUESTIONNAIRE

INTRODUCTION

Good day to you. My name is Evans Momanyi Getembe (PGS/01/2014) a Master of Arts candidate in Sociology at Moi University. I am carrying out research on: “Perception of police officers towards police reforms in Kenya.” This research is part of the requirement for the award of Moi University Masters of Arts in Sociology. You have been selected to participate in this study because you are an officer with National police service and you have been in the service since 2012. Therefore, I humbly request your participation and cooperation. All your views will be held confidentially and will be by no means used for any other purpose outside this study. You are free not to answer any question which you feel not comfortable with. You are also free to pull out of the study at any time. Thank you

➤ *Socio-Demographic*

1. What is your gender Male Female?
2. Tick your appropriate age bracket:
 18-24 25-31 32-38 39-45 46-52 53-59
 60- 66 67 and above
3. What is your level of education?
 Primary Secondary Diploma Degree Masters
 PHD
4. What is your marital Status?
 Single Married
5. What is your religious affiliation?
 Christian Muslim Hindu Atheist

➤ *Work Experience*

6. Where do you currently work?
 Rural Urban
7. What is your current rank in the service?
 Constable Corporal Sergeant Senior Sergeant Inspector Superintendent Senior Superintendent Commissioner of Police
8. State the number of years you have been in the service:
 10- 20 21-30 31- 40 40 - 50
9. Since you joined the police service is this your only police station you have worked?
 Yes No
10. If **yes in question 9**, why?.....
11. If **no in question 9**, Kindly indicate how many stations you have worked:
 1- 5 6-10 11-15 16-20 21-25 Above 26
12. In relation to **question 11**, What are the reason (s) for the number of stations you have worked?.....
13. In relation to question 11, averagely how many years have you worked in one station?
 Less than 1 1-3 4- 6 7-10 11- 14 Below 15
14. What are the reason (s) for the number of years you have worked in each station in question 11?.....
15. Is it a common/normal practice for every officer to work the average number of years in one station in relation question 11?
 Yes No
16. If No in Question 15, Why?.....

➤ *Reforms In Police Services*

• *Knowledge About Police Reforms*

17. Please indicate your opinion regarding the following statement regarding changes in the police

	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Changes in police service aim at making police officers responsible in carrying out their functions/duties					
2	Changes in police service emphasize vetting/screening of police officers to determine their suitability in the service.					
3	Changes in police service aim at involving community members in policing					
4	Changes in police service demands for fair treatment and respect towards clients of police service					
5	Changes in the police aim at improving police officers welfare					

➤ *Attitudes Towards Police Reforms*

18. What is your take regarding the following statement?

	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Changes in police service have made me treat people with respect					
2	Changes in police service have made my delivery of service easy					
3	Changes in police service have motivated me to work hard in my duties					
4	Changes in police service have enhanced fairness in the service					
5	Changes in the police service has increased corruption					

➤ *Practice Towards Police Reforms*

- 19. At individual level, are you comfortable or okay with changes in police service?
() Yes () No
- 20. If yes in question 41, why?.....
- 21. If No in question 41 why?.....
- 22. At individual level, how have these changes in police service informed your performance of your duties?.....
- 23. At individual level what are you doing in relation to these changes in police changes?.....
- 24. What are other police officers doing in relation to these changes?.....
- 25. With the changes are you proud to as a police officer?
() Yes () No

THANK YOU